

GENDER ACTION+

Project acronym:

GENDERACTIONplus

Project title:

Gender Equality Network to Develop ERA Communities To coordinate Inclusive and sustainable policy implementation

Grant agreement No: 101058093

Start date of project: 1 June 2022

Duration: 36 months

Deliverable 2.1

Intersectionality and inclusion

Due date of the deliverable	19.05.2023
Submission date	17.05.2023
File name	D2.1 – Benchmarking report on terminology and policy on intersectionality
Organisation responsible for the deliverable	Kunnskapsdepartementet
Author(s)	Heidi Holt Zachariassen, Ella Ghosh, Ross Woods
Status	Final
Dissemination level	PU

GENDERACTIONplus is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101058093. Views and opinions expressed here are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Revision History			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	31.03.2023	Heidi Holt Zachariassen, Ella Ghosh, Ross Woods	First draft
0.2	13.04.2023	Marcela Linkova	Comments on the first draft
0.3	28.04.2023	Heidi Holt Zachariassen, Ella Ghosh, Ross Woods	Implementation of the comments, including additional information
0.4	05.05.2023	Lydia González Orta	Comments on second draft
0.5	10.05.2023	Heidi Holt Zachariassen, Ella Ghosh, Ross Woods	Implementation of the comments, including additional information
1.0	10.05.2023		Version 2 shared with the Consortium
1.1	15.05. 2023	Heidi Holt Zachariassen, Ella Ghosh	Comments from the Consortium integrated in the draft report. Deliverable sent to coordinator
1.2	16.05.2023	Heidi Holt Zachariassen, Ella Ghosh	Implementation of coordinator's comments on formatting
1.3	17.05.2023	Martina Fucimanová, Marcela Linková	Final formatting
2.0	17.05.2023	Martina Fucimanová	Document submission

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND COUNTRY CODES

Abbreviation	Meaning
AC	Associated Countries
CA	Consortium Agreement
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CoP	Community of Practice
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPN	Data Protection Notice
EGET	European Gender Equality Taskforce
ERA	European Research Area
ERAC SWG GRI	ERAC Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GE	Gender Equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
HE	Higher Education
HLG	EU High Level Group on Non-discrimination, Equality and Diversity
MS	EU Member States
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
R&I	Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

Country codes

Member States of the European Union (EU) and other countries have been assigned a two-letter country code, always written in capital letters, and often used as an abbreviation in statistical analyses, tables, figures or maps.¹

The list below includes abbreviations of EU countries in general and non-EU countries included in this benchmark.

EU Countries

Country	Code	Country	Code	Country	Code	Country	Code
Belgium	(BE)	Greece	(EL)	Lithuania	(LT)	Portugal	(PT)
Bulgaria	(BG)	Spain	(ES)	Luxembourg	(LU)	Romania	(RO)
Czechia	(CZ)	France	(FR)	Hungary	(HU)	Slovenia	(SI)
Denmark	(DK)	Croatia	(HR)	Malta	(MT)	Slovakia	(SK)
Germany	(DE)	Italy	(IT)	The Netherlands	(NL)	Finland	(FI)
Estonia	(EE)	Cyprus	(CY)	Austria	(AT)	Sweden	(SE)
Ireland	(IE)	Latvia	(LV)	Poland	(PL)		

Non-EU Countries

Country	Code
Norway	(NO)
Türkiye	(TR)
Israel	(IL)

¹ Source: EUROSTAT https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Country_codes

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This benchmark report presents the results of a mapping of intersectionality and inclusiveness in R&I legislation and policies in the European Research Area (ERA). It is developed within the ongoing GENDERACTIONplus project, which contributes to the coordination of the gender equality and inclusiveness objectives of the new ERA.

The work on inclusion and intersectionality in GENDERACTIONplus is still at an exploratory phase which is in line with the overall status for this topic in the ERA. This report seeks to improve the knowledge base to give policy input for future work on inclusion and intersectionality in higher education and research and innovation (HE and R&I) in the ERA. A policy brief with recommendations on necessary initiatives at national and European level will follow this report.

Objectives of the report:

- Introduce some relevant theoretical concepts and an overview of EU policy guidelines for the work on diversity, inclusion, and intersectionality.
- Give an overview of the status of inclusive legislation and policies for the HE and R&I sector across MS and AC in the ERA.
- Give an overview of which equality dimensions are included in legislation and policies and the terminology used.
- Identify how several dimensions are addressed in policy documents and legislation by national authorities and research funding organisations (RFOs).
- Give an overview of obstacles and needs when lifting the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the policy agenda.

The results in this report build on the responses of a benchmark survey of 15 European national/regional authorities and 20 research funding organisations (RFOs). The report also provides results from analysing legislation and policy documents provided by the respondents.

Results:

- The field of inclusion and intersectionality is at an initial phase in European research and innovation policies.
- The shift witnessed in European research and innovation policy to a call for an inclusive and intersectional approach is closely linked to a recognition in theory of the shortcomings of a single-dimensional approach to inequality.
- Both national authorities and RFOs indicate that they include many equality dimensions in their legislation and policies. When analysing the attached documents (laws and policies), however, these dimensions are not clearly articulated or discussed at any length.

Survey and legislation/policy analysis – National/regional authorities

- Most countries/ regions in the sample both have legislation and policies at national level that provide guidelines for the work on anti-discrimination/ equal opportunity.
- 10 out of 15 countries/ regions in the sample have national/regional law for HE and R&I that includes gender. 7 out of these countries included more equality dimensions than gender in their law for HE and R&I.
- 6 out of 15 countries/ regions had national/regional policies specifically on gender equality for HE and R&I. 4 of these countries/regions addressed more equality dimensions than gender in their policies for HE and R&I.
- In this sample there were more countries where the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion was addressed in more broadly conceived law/policy than sector-specific multidimensional laws or policies for the HE and R&I sector.
- The equality dimensions addressed the most in legislation for HE and R&I in addition to gender are disability, ethnicity, gender identity, socio-economic status and equality grounds taken together. LGBTQIA+ is addressed the least.
- The equality dimensions addressed the most in policy for HE and R&I (both specific and broadly conceived) in addition to gender were age, socio-economic status, ethnicity, and equality grounds taken together. LGBTQIA+ was addressed the least.
- Terminology that would indicate an inclusive or intersectional approach in policy was used by most respondents where equity/equality, non-discrimination and intersectionality were the terms most frequent in use.
- In our material it was not clear how laws translate into policy and more importantly how discrimination across multiple grounds is addressed in practice. It is also unclear whether multiple grounds are handled separately or with an intersectional approach in policies for HE and R&I.
- There is a variation in starting point in lifting several equality dimensions. Some only work with gender equality and this work is well established, others meet great resistance when promoting gender equality while a few countries already have several dimensions included in policy and active measures.

Survey/policy analysis – research funding organisations (RFOs)

- 19 out of 20 respondents answered that the RFO had a dedicated gender equality policy.
- 14 RFOs answered that their gender equality policies also include other equality dimensions.
- The equality dimensions included the most in RFO policies in addition to gender are disability, gender identity, age, and ethnicity. The dimensions mentioned the least are LGBTQIA+ and equality grounds taken together.
- Terminology that would indicate an inclusive or intersectional approach in policy was used by most respondents where equity/equality, non-discrimination inclusiveness/inclusion, diversity,

and gender+ were the terms most frequent in use. Intersectionality and multiple discrimination were used the least.

- In the policy documents there are traces of intersectional thinking, but no comprehensive examples of a methodology or best practices of systemic intersectional policies.
- RFOs with policies including more dimensions than gender mostly refer to these dimensions in connection with statements of priorities and not practice. No policies had an intersectional approach when discussing several equality dimensions.

Obstacles and needs – national authorities and research funding organisations

- The lack of a unified understanding of concepts and uncertainty about terminology are obstacles identified by both national authorities and RFOs when developing inclusive policies.
- Other obstacles identified by many are lack of disaggregated data, human resources, and national policy.
- For many respondents the work for gender equality is a struggle which makes including other equality dimensions a challenge.
- There is both a need and an interest to lift the intersection of gender with other equality dimensions. Mutual learning initiatives, more research and financial incentives and support are initiatives mentioned by many in addition to a more advanced legal framework at national level and clear guidelines for the EU.

The overall conclusion of this report is that the field of inclusion and intersectionality is at an initial phase in HE and R&I policies in the ERA. Many countries and RFOs are including several equality dimensions in legislation and policies, but they are treated separately or in an additive way. There were few examples of policies with an intersectional approach.

We need to agree on use of terminology and create awareness about the importance of the field of inclusion and intersectionality in HE and R&I. To achieve this, we need to develop a knowledge base of existing and future research combined with improved data collection and examples of good practice. This will help national authorities and RFOs in the ERA translate inclusive policy into action.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. About the project

Building on the Horizon 2020 project GENDERACTION, the overall goal of GENDERACTIONplus is to contribute to the coordination of the gender equality and inclusiveness objectives of the new European Research Area (ERA) through the development of two communities of practice (CoPs), one consisting of representatives of national authorities and the second consisting of representatives of Research Funding Organisations. The network is made up of a total of 22 EU Member States (MS) and 3 Associated Countries (AC), as well as 26 project partners and 14 Associated partners.

Adding the plus sign to the title of the previous GENDERACTION project not only indicates that it is a follow-up project but also makes it explicit that this project also addresses diversity and intersectionality (the gender+ approach).

Specifically, the GENDERACTIONplus project aims to:

- Develop strategic policy advice on existing and emerging policy solutions.
- Enhance the policy-making process by engaging with stakeholders, civil society organisations, and citizens.
- Build capacities, competence, and expertise for gender equality and mainstreaming in Research & Innovation among the policy and RFO community members, with special attention to countries with a less comprehensive policy.
- Create an impact through communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

Thematically, the project focuses on:

- Intersectionality and inclusiveness
- Gender-based violence
- The gender dimension in research and innovation
- Monitoring and evaluating gender equality actions in the European Research Area (ERA)
- Promoting institutional change through Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)

GENDERACTIONplus aims to achieve the following impacts:

- Advance policy coordination among MS and AC countries and through stakeholder and citizen engagement.
- Improve research careers and working conditions in European R&I, by developing policy dialogue and solutions on inclusion and intersectionality, combating gender-based violence, and promoting institutional changes through GEPs.
- Improve research quality and the social responsibility of knowledge by integrating the gender dimension into research and innovation (R&I).
- Reduce geographic inequality by targeting less experienced/engaged countries and regions.

1.2. Objectives of the report

Individual researchers can have different personal characteristics such as racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation or gender identity. They may face intersectional discrimination based on a combination of these characteristics. That is why it is important to take the intersectionality of gender with other grounds of discrimination into account in the work to improve research careers and working conditions in European higher education (HE) and research and innovation (RI).

European policies for research and innovation have increasingly adopted a more inclusive approach. Important strategies such as the The EU gender equality strategy (Union of Equality) ([COM/2020/152final](#)), the Communication from the Commission “A new ERA for Research and Innovation” ([COM/2020/628final](#)) and The Council Conclusions on the New European Research Area ([13567/20](#)) in December 2020, all include inclusion and intersectionality as priorities for the future European politics for research and innovation.

The field of inclusion and intersectionality is at an initial phase in Higher Education and Research and Innovation (HE and R&I) policies in Europe. Building on an informal mapping by the task force on intersectionality in the ERAC Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation (ERAC SWG GRI), the work on inclusion and intersectionality in GENDERACTIONplus is still at an exploratory phase. It seeks to improve the knowledge base to give policy input for future work on inclusion and intersectionality in HE and R&I in Europe.

This report presents the results of benchmarking a sample of European national authorities and research funding organisations (RFOs) on the terminology used and current work on intersectionality, inclusiveness integration in R&I laws and policies across MS and AC. The mapping seeks to find out which governments and RFOs have policy and / or law requirements for work on more equality dimensions than gender in the higher education and research and innovation sector (HE and R&I). We also ask what these dimensions are and how these dimensions are addressed in the relevant policy documents. The mapping has also provided information about the terminology that is frequently used when several discrimination grounds are addressed. We look at whether the respondents’ policies and/ or laws take on an additive/ multidimensional approach or an intersectional approach (for definitions see Chapter 3. Theoretical background). Finally, the report also gives an overview of obstacles and needs identified by the sample when lifting the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the policy agenda.

This benchmark report provides a current picture in relation to diversity, inclusion and intersectionality in European HE and R&I. The results of the benchmark and what the respondents have identified as the main obstacles and needs to lift inclusion and intersectionality on the policy agenda, will be the foundation for future policy input and recommendations for emphasis on diversity, inclusion and intersectionality in European HE and R&I. A policy brief will follow this report based on its main findings and conclusions. It will be co-created with relevant stakeholders in WP 8 who are responsible for communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities of the GENDERACTIONplus project. The aim is to maximise the impact of the report findings.

1.3. The relationship of this report to other tasks and work packages

WP2 Intersectionality and inclusiveness will feed the other thematic WPs. It is specific in that intersectionality and inclusiveness must be mainstreamed into WP 3–6 to ensure that an inclusive perspective can start to be developed in EU HE and R&I policy making and coordination. There are for instance high expectations at the EU level regarding the inclusion of an intersectional perspective

in the content of R&I (the focus of WP4) as well as regarding the design and implementation of inclusive Gender Equality Plans (the focus of WP6). For this purpose, the survey questions for the mapping in WP 3-6 included separate questions on intersectionality and inclusion as an effort to identify the current status of these policies and to mainstream this topic into all thematic WPs.

Based on the benchmarking results, exchanges with stakeholders and experts will be organised, to ensure quality and communication of the benchmarking findings to a wider group of stakeholders and citizens, as a preparation for further dissemination and feeding into policy development (an EU impact plan will be developed in the framework of this project). The results will also be the basis for action development in National Impact Plans (NIPs) and the co-creation for citizen and stakeholder engagement.

1.4. Structure of the report

This report starts with a description of the policy backdrop for the work on diversity, inclusion and intersectionality in Higher Education and Research and Innovation (HE and R&I) politics in Europe (Chapter 2). For the sake of analysis and because diversity, inclusion and intersectionality are terms which many are not familiar with, a separate theoretical chapter (Chapter 3) is dedicated to present a theoretical background.

In chapter 5 we present the results of the benchmark survey and the analysis of attached laws and policies provided by our respondents. The chapter is divided into two parts, one for national authorities and one for Research Funding Organisations (RFOs). The chapter ends with identifying cross-cutting issues between national authorities and RFOs. The findings will also be discussed in relation to how they correspond to the conclusions in other recent studies on inclusive gender equality in European HE and R&I. This report ends with a summary and conclusions that will be the basis for future input to policy recommendations for lifting diversity, inclusion, and intersectionality higher on the agenda in European HE and R&I.

2. POLICY BACKGROUND

For the past few years, we have witnessed a shift in European research and innovation policies from a single focus on gender equality to an increasing use of the terminology on inclusion, diversity and intersectionality that now also has manifested itself in the main EU policy developments for the research and innovation sector.

European research policy has for many years been a driving force for setting gender equality in research and innovation on the agenda at European level and within its member states (MS) and associated countries (AC). It was a watershed when the European Research Area (ERA), identified gender equality as one of its priority areas for research and innovation. The three areas of priority for gender in the ERA were integrated in Framework Programme Horizon 2020: Gender balance in research teams, gender balance in decision-making positions and integration of gender dimension in research and innovation. (GENDERACTION briefing paper n1, 2018)

With an increasing recognition, also long before the policy initiatives mentioned above, that gender inequality does not operate separately from other equality dimensions in European research policies (Lombardo and Verloo 2009), European research policy has gradually shifted its focus from a single dimension to a multi-dimensional approach ([UniSAFE 2021b](#)). This was gradually evident in important

policy papers increasingly using terminology such as inclusion, diversity, and intersectionality where different discrimination grounds such as ethnicity, religion, social background and disability were identified. This shift is now also manifested in instrumental policy documents that both define and give direction to European research and innovation policies for the future. These are first and foremost the EU Gender Equality Strategy (Union of Equality) ([COM/2020/152final](#)), that clearly stated that intersectionality would be used as a cross-cutting principle throughout the whole strategy. This was reaffirmed in the Communication “A new ERA for Research and Innovation” and The Council Conclusions on the New European Research Area (ERA) in December 2020 (Approaches to inclusive gender equality in research and innovation, [European Union, 2022](#)).

EU MS and AC have committed to take action and support the work for gender equality and inclusion through the European Research Area (ERA) and its policy agenda (ERA Policy Agenda Action 5: Promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness) and by signing the Ljubljana Declaration on Gender Equality in Research and Innovation. (Ibid). In addition, Horizon Europe, with its eligibility criteria on inclusive Gender Equality Plans, will affect each country’s research and innovation sector as they now will have to try to identify and execute actions for inclusive gender equality to meet this requirement.

The EU also has relevant policy initiatives and strategies which incorporate aspects of intersectionality, and specific funding mechanisms that support policies and practices to encourage intersectionality measures at Member State level. These include the following EU strategies, policies, and guidelines:

- EU Anti- Racism Action Plan 2020-2025 ([COM \(2020\) 565 final](#))
- Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021-2030 ([COM \(2021\) 101 final](#))
- EU Roma Strategic Framework for Equality, Inclusion and Participation 2020-2030 ([COM \(2020\) 620 final](#))
- LGBTIQ Equality Strategy 2020-2025 ([COM 2020 698 final](#))

Also, other important bodies that influence the research and innovation sector have set focus on a more inclusive and multidimensional approach in their equality work. European University Association (EUA) INVITED project aimed to support universities in developing strategies towards equity, diversity, and inclusion (EUA, 2019). The League of European Research Universities ([LERU, 2019](#)) and The Guild ([2022](#)) have an inclusive and multidimensional approach to their work on equality, illustrated through position papers and events.

To support its initiatives, the European Commission has commissioned research and tools to improve the knowledge-base and map the status for inclusive gender equality work and give guidance for future work. Recent work on the topic includes the report Approaches to inclusive gender equality in research and innovation (Ibid) and the Pilot assessment activities for the European knowledge and facility on GEPs in research and innovation organisations (European Commission 2023; not yet published). In both these reports and in the position papers referred to above, it was concluded that working with several equality dimensions or having an intersectional approach is an emerging field of work and that it is only possible to identify policies and good practices in a few European countries. Countries that are often referred to are Ireland, Germany, The Netherlands, Norway, and the United Kingdom. In this benchmarking report we came to the same conclusions.

The expansion in She Figures to include a policy brief on intersectionality has added knowledge about the lack of an indicator which fully addresses the concept of intersectionality. An exploratory indicator was tested as a starting point, but further development of this indicator will be needed in the future so that an intersectional analysis can be included in future She Figures publications (European Union 2021). In addition, the task force on intersectionality in the ERAC Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation (ERAC SWG GRI) did an informal mapping in 2020 on emerging work for

inclusion and intersectionality as a basis for an exchange of views among its members. Intersectionality was recommended as a future focus area by the ERAC SWG GRI in the Position paper on the future gender equality priority in the ERA 2020-2030 ([ERAC 1204/20](#)).

Acknowledging the importance of equality data, in February 2018, the EU High Level Group on Non-discrimination, Equality and Diversity (HLG)² set up the Subgroup on Equality Data to help MS improve the collection and use of equality data. Such data may enable policymakers to assess the scale and nature of discrimination suffered by vulnerable and marginalised groups. The HLG works on the following grounds of discrimination: sexual orientation and gender identity, racial or ethnic origin, age, religion or belief and disability, with gender being taken into consideration in its intersection with these grounds. According to the HLG, data collection on the discrimination grounds of racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, sexual orientation and gender identity tends to be the least developed in MS. Furthermore, such imbalances in equality data collection can lead to a lack of evidence on the extent to which people experience multiple and intersectional discrimination. To help Member states with a consistent approach on equality data collection, the Subgroup on Equality Data has developed various guidelines.

- In 2018 the HLG adopted non-binding guidelines on how to improve the collection and use of equality data; Guidelines on improving the collection and use of equality data 2018 ([European Union 2018](#))
- In 2021 the HLG published guidelines to Member States on improving the collection of data disaggregated by racial or ethnic origin. Guidance note on the collection and use of equality data based on racial or ethnic origin 2021 ([European Union 2021](#))
- An EU Commission report from 2017 provides country level analysis and relevant information on the national legal frameworks, policies, and activities in the field of equality data collection in the EU Member States. ([European Commission 2017](#))

3. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

There are many reasons why equality policies should take on an intersectional approach.

- By including several equalities dimensions it exposes different types of discrimination and disadvantage. This *reflects the reality of discrimination as discriminated groups are never homogeneous*.
- From a more practical point of view, taking on an intersectional approach *can lead to identifying more efficient and relevant measures* as it will address different types of needs and situations of marginalized disadvantaged groups in a holistic way (Advisory Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2020).
- Introducing intersectionality as an analytical lens and tool when advocating for equality in academia *can be transformative in that it identifies the need for institutional change for the multiple marginalized faculties*.

² The EU High Level Group on Non-Discrimination, Equality and Diversity was established in 2015 to deepen cooperation and coordination between Member States and the Commission on achieving diversity and full equality in practice and eliminating discrimination. The lack of coherent, systematic, and relevant equality data may be a barrier to addressing patterns of discrimination and developing and implementing effective policy action.

- An intersectional lens can *challenge the equality policies and measures* within higher education institutions (HEIs) and thereby *challenge the invisibility of some social identities and experiences*, such as those of women of colour.
- An intersectional approach can *address how designing and implementing policies can become more effective in tackling harassment and inequality in academia* (Täuber 2022).
- By considering the workings of multiple systems of disadvantage across grounds such as gender, ethnicity, and class, *it is not possible to simply focus on academic career and progression without considering how social and personal factors affect an academic advancement differently* for people of different backgrounds (Nichols and Stahl 2019).

The shift witnessed in EU policy to the use of and the call for an inclusive and intersectional approach to the research sectors work for equality, is closely linked to a recognition in theory of the shortcomings of a single-dimensional approach to inequality which has created a need for an inclusive and intersectional approach.

Often the terms diversity, inclusion and intersectionality are used interchangeably in policy documents although they mean different things. Another term that is relevant to include for the purpose of this report is equality or gender equality which, as referred to in chapter 2 Policy background, has been the focus for the work on equality in academia for the past decades. Equality is connected to the idea that all humans have the same rights and therefore should enjoy equal treatment and non-discrimination. (EUA Invited 2019) Discrimination defines a situation where an individual is disadvantaged in some way on the basis of one or multiple protected grounds (Handbook on European Non-discrimination Law 2018). As the gender balance in academic positions has been uneven, the focus on gender equality has meant that men and women should have the same rights, access to and possibility to achieve an academic career.

The gradual introduction of additional discriminatory grounds in the work for equal access and treatment in academia, has made the terms diversity and inclusion more common in use. Diversity is a multi-dimensional concept that includes several different categories such as ethnicity, gender, age, sexual orientation and social background or class. The groups identified with these equality dimensions have received special attention as they in different ways are identified as underrepresented, disadvantaged, or vulnerable in an academic setting (Ibid.). As the awareness has evolved of the need to broaden the scope on equality work to involve more dimensions, the focus on inclusion has been introduced. This means that leaders and institutions must work to make researchers of different backgrounds and qualifications feel integrated and included in an academic setting. The ultimate goal is to create a feeling of belonging in academia for all. Diversity and inclusion already point to the need to be aware of and cater for that inequality and discrimination in academia need to be treated with a multi-dimensional lens. Intersectionality takes this one step further, looking at how different dimensions of power relations cooperate and are experienced in different ways.

Coined by the feminist legal scholar Kimberlé Crenshaw (Crenshaw 1989), the concept of intersectionality has since its inception been developed and discussed in different disciplines and contexts identifying what the concept can bring to the work against inequality and discrimination and how to apply it to policy and equality work in practice. The term intersectionality starts from the premise that people live multiple, layered identities derived from social relations, history, and the operation of structures of power. Intersectional analysis aims to reveal multiple identities, exposing the different types of intersectional and multiple discrimination and disadvantage that occur as a consequence of the combination of identities and the intersection of sex and gender with other grounds. (EIGE, [intersectionality | European Institute for Gender Equality \(europa.eu\)](https://eige.europa.eu/intersectionality))

This term acknowledges that men and women are not homogeneous groups, but that also ethnic and social background, religion, gender identity or disability intersect and are inseparable shaping an individual's identity and experiences. An intersectional approach does not, however, take into consideration only the intersecting aspects of an individual's identity or positionalities, but also the intersecting forces of privilege and oppression operating in a specific context (Palmén 2021). Intersectionality thus visualizes how multiple axes of discrimination and oppression interact and illustrates and identifies unique experiences of inequality and injustice felt by individuals with intersecting identities (Täuber 2022).

The shift in focus from “women” being thought about as a homogenous group and thereby sharing common experiences—to a more nuanced approach is a welcomed move. It recognizes how multiple sources of disadvantage and privilege operate and thereby accounts for how individuals may experience multiple sources of discrimination and oppression (Palmén, 2021). In higher education and research, an intersectional approach is thus important because it acknowledges and visualizes that researchers and scientists are not a homogeneous group. They come from different backgrounds and have different experiences which can be sources of privilege and disadvantage affecting their career prospects and progression and also the feeling of inclusion and belonging in academia. (She Figures, 2021). It is important to mention, however, that intersectionality as a concept has also been criticized. Examples of criticism is that it is difficult to understand, as there is no unified definition, and to apply in practice. Some criticizes the concept as only used for paying “lip-service” to underrepresented groups and yet others criticizes that there is no defined intersectional methodology (Christoffersen, A. 2021, Collins, P.H., da Silva, E.C.G., Ergun, E. *et al.* 2021, Nash, J. C. 2008).

With an increased focus on diversity, inclusion and intersectionality in higher education and research, we can identify different approaches to how including and addressing more discriminatory grounds is materialized in policy and equality actions. We can identify three different approaches: 1) the Gender+ approach 2) the additive/multi-dimensional and 3) the intersectional approach.

1) As gender equality has been the main focus of intervention for a long time, some actions and policies only extend this focus by including more dimensions of discrimination in addition to gender. This is often referred to as a gender+-approach. (European Commission 2022). This approach has, however, been criticized for not being intersectional, but merely an add on to the ongoing work for gender equality where gender is the main and prioritized equality dimension for action.

2) The most common approach is the additive or multi-dimensional approach that treats a person's belonging to different strands of diversity, for example woman and an ethnic minority, separately. (Advisory Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2020, UniSAFE 2021b). This approach builds on the protection afforded to individuals through antidiscrimination legislation and EU directives against discrimination. It is based on an understanding of differential treatment that disadvantages individuals due to gender, sexual identity/orientation, disability, ethnicity, religion etc. This is an approach that has been criticized for not being dynamic enough essentializing and treating the different discriminatory grounds individually as if they mattered equally not considering how they operate together and in different contexts (UniSAFE 2021b). For example, in policies and identified measures for equality work, we often see that each discriminatory ground is defined and treated separately not taking into consideration how they intersect, and that each person may experience them differently depending on their background. This “weak approach” as described by Susanne Täuber, “will yield additive insights that treat identities as if they were separate, independent and could be ranked” (Täuber 2022: 2).

3) An intersectional approach differs from the two aforementioned approaches in that it addresses the different discrimination grounds and how they are experienced by different individuals as “synergistic”.

This means that intersectional experiences are greater than the sum of separate axes of oppression or discrimination such as sexism or racism and are therefore inseparable. Including and combining various discrimination grounds, as an intersectional approach does, produces something unique and distinct from any one form of discrimination standing alone (Advisory Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2020).

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1. Target groups

The benchmarking survey targeted national authorities (ministries, national agencies and organisations that support them) and research funding organisations (RFOs). Overall, 113 representatives of national authorities, supporting organisations and RFOs within and outside the consortium were addressed with a request to (help to) ensure the answers to the questionnaires.

4.2. Data collection

The benchmarking survey was disseminated on 10.10.2022 with the deadline on 6.11.2022. In the case of some respondents, there was an agreement to postpone the deadline (often because of the need to coordinate the collection of information for the questionnaire across the organisation and/or because of the heavy workload in the autumn and as the end of the year approaches). The last inputs have been received on 18.11.2022.

4.3. Mapping instruments

The data were gathered through the LimeSurvey platform. To facilitate the work of coordinating inputs, a Word version of the questionnaires was sent to respondents along with a link to the questionnaire in the outreach email. Most of the inputs were entered via online questionnaire, in two cases (SK, BE) the answers were sent in a word document.

4.4. Data clearing

All data with survey answers was downloaded from LimeSurvey as an excel files. Attached documents were mostly in PDF format (only exceptionally in Word files). There were overall 50 attached documents in the survey in the case of national policies benchmarking survey and 14 among responses of RFOs.

In the excel files with answers partial adjustments have been made to the a few initial questions in respondents' inputs, e.g., change or adding of country name to country code (Poland => PL, Spain=>ES), in one case the name of organisation was omitted by the respondent and was therefore added in the data cleaning phase. The two answers to the survey submitted in Word file have been manually added to the excel files.

In the next step, the answers that were complete were filtered. The duplicate inputs have been omitted. As a result, there were 20 answers from RFOs (out of 29 addressed) and 15 questionnaires describing national and regional policies (out of 23 countries, whose representatives of national authorities or supporting organisations were asked for inputs).

4.5. Data analysis

Survey analysis

The main source for all findings was the benchmark report for National/Regional and RFO policies. The number of units was so low that we chose to use simple frequency diagrams made in Excel rather than using more sophisticated statistical tools.

Text answers were converted into numerical format. When making figures, answers were usually sorted alphabetically or by frequency. We chose to focus on frequency rather than institutions in figures. Each figure has a corresponding table to allow the reader to see how various responding countries/ regions or RFOs have answered. This format was chosen instead of colour coded figures to facilitate easy identification.

National authorities: The 15 respondents were first categorised in different groups according to the type of legislation and policy the country/region had. In the second step, we clustered countries/regions in groups according to if they had broadly conceived multidimensional policies for HE and R&I (7 units) or multidimensional gender equality policies for HE and R&I (4 units) as explained in Chapter 5.1.1. Some tables and figures were generated for the whole group of 15 respondents, and some only for the 7+4 countries with multidimensional policies for HE and R&I.

Research funding organisations: Out of the 20 RFOs that were in the survey, 19 were selected as relevant for the benchmark on intersectionality because they had a gender equality policy. For the most part, answers from all 19 respondents were used throughout. 5 countries out of the 19 did not have gender equality policies with additional dimensions, but their answers proved to be of great interest on questions regarding needs and obstacles.

Document analysis

National authorities: In the sample of 15 national authorities, 7 countries reported having national/regional laws for HE and R&I that address the topic of equality, diversity, and inclusion, while 5 countries reported having broadly conceived national/regional laws for HE and R&I that address the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion. 7 countries reporting having broadly conceived multidimensional policies for HE and R&I, while 4 countries reporting having multidimensional gender equality policies for HE and R&I. All respondents provided text and/or links to relevant documents. These documents were analysed to ascertain which dimensions in addition to gender equality were addressed in these policies/laws, what terms were most frequently in relation to equality, diversity, and inclusion, and to identify patterns emerging in policies/laws which address additional grounds of discrimination beyond gender.

Research funding organizations: In the sample of 19 research funding organizations (RFOs) 14 organizations indicated that their gender policy included more discrimination grounds. The five organizations that answered that they did not have a gender policy were asked if the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion were addressed in more broadly conceived policies and strategies. None of these RFOs had such documents and are therefore not included in the text analysis. The 14 RFOs with gender policies including other discrimination grounds were asked to specify relevant passages in their document to exemplify this. Some RFOs only included text excerpts, while others attached texts and documents where more discrimination grounds were mentioned. To find out in what way the discrimination grounds were described and translated into practice, all documents and text excerpts were studied. In addition, all the attached documents were reviewed to cross-check what was provided in the textual responses to the survey and to find out if there were other sections of relevance in the

documents. In order to help us find passages of relevance we the terms intersectionality, diversity, age, disability, ethnicity, identity, religion was the focus of this review.

For identifying how multiple equality dimensions were addressed in the document analysis of national/regional laws and policies and RFO policies, the definitions provided in the theory chapter (Chapter 3, theoretical background) were used.

4.6. Limitations

There were several limitations discovered in the data during the analysis phase. Some were caused by our survey design, others had external causes beyond our control.

One limitation that affected the depth of the text analysis regarding national authorities and RFOs is that only a few of the respondents sent excerpts from their policies in both groups. Another limitation is that the material did not give us information on actions taken by national authorities and RFOs, unless this was specifically mentioned in survey responses.

A condition that may have affected the amount and type of material we received is that we asked about whether the respondents' gender equality policy also included other discrimination grounds. This can indicate that we inadvertently steered respondents in the direction of examples of *gender+* work.

Some countries are not part of this survey (or did not respond to this survey) that we know have interesting work on more discrimination grounds than gender. The non-response from interesting actors has limited the results of the survey regarding good examples of intersectional work.

When analysing benchmark responses to the policy benchmark we understood our findings on obstacles (See question 5.8, discussed in Chapter 5) were limited due to the *routing format* chosen. That means that if a respondent provides a particular answer, then they are directed to a particular page in the survey. The routing assumed that a sizeable number of respondents would have sector level gender equality policy. In retrospect it would have been fruitful to ask two questions about possible obstacles, one for those that have such strategies, another for those who do not. A corresponding routing limitation was set for a question on supportive measures (Question 5.9 in the policy benchmark).

We could compare answers from 15 national/ regional authorities and 19 RFOs at a general level, but not country by country. There are also limitations in the possibility to consider if and how RFOs are influenced by authorities in our sample. This was due to a lack of congruence between RFO and policy responses. There were 5 RFOs that answered from countries where authorities did not respond. There were four cases where only authorities, not RFOs responded. There were 9 country responses where 1 or 2 RFOs also responded, i.e., overlap of RFOs and authorities.

The map below may explain the lack of congruence between RFOs and national authorities in this benchmark. The map has four categories – countries that responded at authority level alone, countries that responded at RFO level alone, countries with both types of respondents, and countries with no response (among EU countries). The map illustrates that though there is a high number of respondents in the sample, only a few countries have respondents from both RFOs and national/ regional authorities. This reduces the possibility to make valid comparisons of responses from RFOs and authorities and makes it difficult to evaluate effects of policy signals from authorities on RFO policies.

Figure 1 Map of respondents at policy and RFO level

- 0 Countries not responding in the study were France, Germany, The Netherlands, Hungary, Finland, Iceland etc.
- 1 Only policy level: Austria, Croatia, Greece, and Israel
- 2 Only RFO: RIF (Cyprus), ETAB (Estonia), FRRB (Italy), MCST (Malta) & UEFISCDI (Romania)
- 3 Both policy/RFO: Belgium, Czech Republic, Ireland, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain & Sweden

The colour scale goes from pale (nonresponding) to dark (both policy/RFO).

5. RESULTS

5.1. National authorities

5.1.1. An overview of the findings in the survey and document analysis

Key findings

- Most countries/ regions in the sample both have legislation and policies at national level that provide guidelines for the work on anti-discrimination/ equal opportunity.
- Only 7 countries/regions had laws and 4 countries/regions had policies with more equality dimensions than gender specifically for the HE and R&I sector.
- In this sample there were more countries where the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion was addressed in more broadly conceived law/policy than sector specific multidimensional laws or policies in the HE and R&I sector.
- In our material it was not clear how laws translate into policy and more importantly how discrimination across multiple grounds is addressed in practice. It is also unclear whether multiple grounds are handled separately or with an intersectional approach in policies for HE and R&I.
- A pattern emerges that implies national laws, which are in turn based on international human rights and EU legislation, must focus on the protection of multiple but separate equality grounds. Given this legal necessity, it appears that the translation of intersectionality into legislation can be challenging.
- There is a legislative imperative to work on multiple equality grounds, which in turn means that there is potential for policy to reflect this and to adopt or encourage an intersectional approach, particularly in instances where countries have already developed gender equality-specific strategies.
- While national authorities can set requirements for RPOs and RFOs to approach gender equality from an intersectional perspective, it is perhaps only possible to see how this is translated into practice through analysis of institutional GEPs and their implementation.
- The countries in our sample identify the use of a wide variety of inclusive terminology in policies. This means that national authorities in MS and ACs increasingly meet EU-policy expectations on an increased use of inclusive language.
- There are important contextual factors which show the variation in starting point for different countries; some have difficulty lifting gender equality while other countries already have several dimensions included in policy and active measures.

In this section we present the results from the part of the benchmarking survey undertaken in 2022 focusing on national legislation and policies for the higher education, research, and innovation sector (HE and R&I) in several European countries. The results presented in this chapter are the replies to the part of the survey where the purpose was to identify which national authorities have laws and policies that address more discrimination grounds than gender and whether intersectional perspectives are included in HE and R&I law and policy. The survey provides information about the most common discrimination grounds and terminology included in policies and laws. The respondents also give input on what initiatives and knowledge are needed to lift the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the policy agenda. This chapter includes results from the analysis of attached laws and policies to illustrate and nuance the findings in the survey.

Respondents to this survey were mainly employed in ministries or associated organisations with knowledge of/responsibility for following up equality in higher education and research and innovation (HE and R&I). Altogether 15 representatives of national authorities from 14 countries (2 respondents from Belgium) responded to this survey.

In the following, we first present relevant legislation and policy at national and sector level, i.e., national laws and policy for equality/discrimination and laws and policies for HE and R&I level which includes gender equality. In the next section, we focus on countries with policy and legislation that addresses more discrimination grounds than gender equality.

Overview of relevant legislation and policy at national and sector level

In this part of the survey the intention was to identify whether the responding countries/ regions have national/ regional legislation and policies in place in HE and R&I on anti-discrimination and/ or equal opportunity that could serve as a guideline and influence sector specific legislation and policies. The table below groups countries according to whether they have equality/antidiscrimination legislation and policies at national level, and whether they have equality dimensions in legislation or gender equality policies specifically for the HE and R&I sector. The categories are not mutually exclusive, so some countries are in two or three of these clusters. Purple is used to indicate law, grey to indicate policy.

As seen in Table 1 below, 15 countries/regions in this mapping have national equality/anti-discrimination law, while 10 have national/regional law for HE and R&I that includes gender equality. Altogether 13 respondents have national/regional equality or equal opportunity policies. Six countries have gender equality policies for HE and R&I.

Table 1 Legislation and policy at national level and at HE and R&I level

	Type of legislation and policy	Responses	Country/region
National	A) Countries with national/regional anti-discrimination and/or equal opportunity laws ³	15	Austria, Belgium-Flanders, Belgium-FWB, Croatia, Czech Republic Denmark, Greece Ireland, Israel, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden,
	B) Countries with national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy ⁴	13	Belgium-Flanders, Belgium-FWB, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Greece, Ireland, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden
Higher education & Research/	C) Countries with national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality ⁵	10 (9)	Austria, Belgium-Flanders, Belgium-FWB, Croatia, Greece, Israel, Lithuania, Norway, Spain, Sweden

³ 2.1 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination and/or equal opportunity laws?

⁴ 2.2 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy?

⁵ 4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?

Innovation (HE and R&I)	D) Countries with national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation ⁶	6 (5)	Belgium-Flanders, Belgium-FWB, Croatia, Ireland, Israel, Spain
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The results from the survey presented above, indicate that most countries/ regions in the sample both have legislation and policies at national level that provide guidelines for the work on anti-discrimination/ equal opportunity. Also, at HE and R&I level many of the responding countries / regions have legislation and policies for gender equality. With so many countries having legislation and policies on anti-discrimination and equal opportunity in place, it makes up a good framework for the HE and R&I sector in these countries to have laws and policies including more equality dimensions than gender. That means that there are no legal barriers to including more dimensions than gender at sector level.

From stating that most countries in our sample have a good legal and policy framework at national and HE and R&I level for inclusive laws and policies, we narrow the scope and focus on those countries in our sample that have multidimensional laws/ policies for HE and R&I; laws and policies including gender *and other* equality dimensions. Countries with inclusive laws and policies are supplemented by countries with *broadly conceived laws or national/regional policies/strategies* for HE and R&I where equality dimensions beyond gender equality are addressed. It may not be immediately apparent what is meant by broadly conceived laws or policies or strategies. Examples of such documents, supplied by the respondents, are a National Research Career Strategy and Long-term plan for research and higher education (NO), a State Scientific Policy (PL) and a strategy for Impact Driven Management (AT). Other documents that are broadly conceived can be antidiscrimination laws at national level that mention higher education specifically (SE).

From national level to HE and R&I level – inclusive laws and policies

In the table below countries/regions are grouped according to whether they have *specific inclusive policies and laws for HE and R&I* or *broadly conceived inclusive policies and laws for HE and R&I*. In the table, this is referred to as multidimensional law or policy. The categories are not mutually exclusive, so some countries are included in two or three of these clusters. Purple is used to indicate law, grey to indicate policy. Readers should bear in mind that this table is a description of the variety among respondents when it comes to multidimensional laws and policies. This benchmarking exercise does not evaluate the relative merits of different models of national and sector-level policy or legislation.

⁶ 4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?

Table 2 National authorities with multidimensional laws and policies for HE and R&I

	Type of law and policy	Responses	Countries
Multidimensional law or policy for HE and R&I	I. Countries with a national/regional law for HE+RI that addresses more equality dimensions than gender ⁷	7	Austria, Belgium-FWB, Croatia, Greece, Lithuania, Norway, Spain
	II. Countries with a national/regional policy on gender equality for HE+RI that addresses more equality dimensions than gender ⁸	4	Belgium-FWB, Croatia, Ireland, Spain
Broadly conceived laws or policies for HE and R&I that are multidimensional	III: Countries where the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion is addressed in a more broadly conceived national/regional law for HE+RI ⁹	5	Czech Republic, Ireland, Israel, Poland, Portugal
	IV. Countries where the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion is addressed in a more broadly conceived national/regional policy for HE+RI? ¹⁰	7	Austria, Greece, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Sweden

In this sample there are more countries where the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion is addressed in more broadly conceived law/policy than sector specific multidimensional laws or policies in the HE and R&I sector. Clusters of countries in category II and IV, where diversity is addressed in policy, are given particular attention in this chapter. However, given the assumption that policy for HE and R&I in a country is affected by how discrimination grounds/equality dimensions are addressed in sector law (category I) it is of interest to look at which and how many equality dimensions are included in legislation for HE and R&I.

⁷ 5.1 Does the national/regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation address one or more of the following dimensions?

⁸ 5.4 If you have a national/regional policy on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, does this policy also address one or more of the following dimensions?

⁹ 5.3 If you do not have a national/regional law on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in a more broadly conceived national/regional law for higher education, research and innovation?

¹⁰ If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies, etc.)?

Equality dimensions included in HE and R&I legislation

One of the goals of this benchmarking is to identify the status of whether and how intersectionality and inclusiveness are integrated in R&I laws and policies across Member states (MS) and Associated countries (AC). However, it is also of interest to know which discrimination grounds are addressed in laws in this benchmark.

To identify in what way policies and legislation are inclusive, the respondents with laws including more dimensions than gender, were asked to identify the dimensions included¹¹. Below we present what other equality dimensions than gender that are most prevalent in HE and R&I legislation.

10 respondents (9 countries including both regions of Belgium) have HE-laws that include gender equality¹². 7 out of these 10 respondents answered that other grounds of discrimination were also included in this legislation. See Table 2 (Category 1). These countries are Austria, Belgium-FWB, Croatia, Greece, Lithuania, Norway, and Spain.

Figure 2 Equality dimensions addressed in HE and R&I legislation

Table 3 Countries with legislation with multidimensional HE and R&I legislation

Dimensions	Countries where national/regional law for HE and R&I address one or more of the following dimensions
Age	Austria, Greece, Lithuania
Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)	Belgium, Greece, Lithuania, Norway
Disability	Austria, Belgium-FWB, Greece, Lithuania
Ethnicity	Austria, Greece, Lithuania, Spain
Gender identity	Austria, Croatia, Greece, Lithuania

¹¹ 5.1 Does the national/regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation address one or more of the following dimensions?

¹² Austria, Belgium Flanders, Belgium FWB, Croatia, Greece, Israel, Lithuania, Norway, Spain, and Sweden

LGBTQI+	Greece, Lithuania
Religion	Austria, Greece, Lithuania
Sexual orientation	Austria, Greece, Lithuania
Socio-economic status	Austria, Greece, Lithuania, Spain

Some of the countries in our sample have included many grounds (e.g. Lithuania, Austria, Greece), some with a catchall category – Inequality grounds taken together^[1] (e.g. Norway). We can therefore say that they are multidimensional. As the objective of this study is to identify whether legislation and policy for HE and R&I in our sample has an intersectional approach, the texts referred to by respondents have been analysed to understand how multiple equality dimensions are addressed in legislation.

^[1] After going through the responses, we realize that the category “Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)” is ambiguous: It can be perceived as an acknowledgment of all protected grounds in national antidiscrimination laws or an integrated or inclusive approach of many dimensions. This is not clear without delving into how the separate dimensions and their interaction are understood in laws and policies.

National/regional laws for HE and R&I that address one or more dimensions of equality

Figure A and Table 3 show us that seven countries in the sample include several equality dimensions in their legislation. We can therefore say they are multidimensional. An analysis of the documents provided by respondents reveals some patterns. National legislation, whether targeted specifically or not at higher education and/ or research and innovation, protects citizens on multiple equality grounds, yet it is unclear how this protection is undertaken from an intersectional perspective. In most instances, except for Spain, it appears that the legal protections provided are given either separately or through an additive approach. Of further interest in the context of this benchmarking exercise is the varying terminology that emerges from these documents. Terms such as “equal treatment” (AT, LT) and “equal opportunities” are used to define equality more broadly (AT), while a number of MS laws discuss both “direct discrimination” and “indirect discrimination” (AT, BE-FWB, LT) are provided (in both categories of discrimination). In the case of Austria, the inclusion of “multiple discrimination” points to the potential for an intersectional approach, which in this particular instance, allows for increased compensation when an individual is discriminated against across multiple equality grounds. What remains unclear is how these laws translate into policy and more importantly how discrimination across multiple grounds is addressed in practice. This will be a point of discussion in the analysis of policy documents that follows below.

In **Austria**, Universities, University Colleges of Teacher Education and the Austrian Academy of Science have to apply the Federal Equal Treatment Act. This Act focuses on gender in first instance but does refer to other characteristics, specifically “*equal treatment regardless of ethnicity, religion or belief, age or sexual orientation (anti-discrimination)*”. In terms of an intersectional understanding of discrimination, this Act recognises “multiple discrimination”, stating that “*If there is multiple discrimination for the reasons specified in Section 4 or Section 13 (1), this must be taken into account when assessing the amount of compensation for the personal impairment suffered.*”

In **Belgium**, the Ministry of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation cites the Décret relatif à la lutte contre certaines formes de discrimination, which references multiple grounds of discrimination as follows: “Protected criteria”: *nationality, alleged race, skin colour, descent or national or ethnic origin, age, sexual orientation, religious or philosophical belief, disability, sex and assimilated criteria such as*

pregnancy, childbirth and maternity, or sex reassignment, gender identity and gender expression, marital status, birth, wealth, political conviction, language, current or future state of health, a physical or genetic characteristic, social origin or union conviction”.

In **Greece**, national legislation dictates that Gender Equality Committees are established in HEIs as advisory bodies of the Senates and the Administrations of the Faculties and Departments of the HEIs for the promotion of equality at all levels of operation and in all processes of academic life. One of the most important responsibilities of the Gender Equality Committees is the preparation of medium-term Action Plans for Gender Equality for each HEI. While this legislation focuses specifically on gender equality, it does refer to a broader conception of equality, for instance: When selecting Senate members in a HEI *“the contribution of the candidates in the fields of gender equality, the fight against inequalities and discrimination and the fight against social exclusion”* should be taken into account (our emphasis). While described as Gender Equality Committee, the committee’s legal responsibilities include (my emphasis):

- *preparing action plans to promote and ensure substantial equality in the educational, research and administrative procedures of the Foundation and prepares an annual report, which it submits to the Senate,*
- *recommending to the competent bodies measures to promote equality and combat sexism,*
- *providing information and training to members of the academic community on issues related to gender and equality.*

In **Spain**, the national law specifically references the need to take an intersectional approach when promoting a gender perspective in scientific and technical research: *“a gender perspective [will be promoted] in all aspects of scientific and technical research, including, where appropriate, intersectionality with other relevant aspects, such as socio-economic status or ethnicity”.* Further, it dictates that *“measures to integrate intersectionality both in the design of gender equality policies in science and innovation and in the content of research and knowledge transfer”* will be adopted. As can be noted, socio-economic status and ethnicity are the additional grounds that are specifically referenced in the law.

Croatia references its national Law on Higher Education and Scientific Activity, although there is no clear reference to equality grounds except for a reference to the fact that expressions used in this Law, which have a gender meaning, refer equally to the male and female genders.

In **Lithuania**, the Law on Equal Treatment enshrines *“the equality of persons and prohibition against restrictions on human rights or extensions of privileges on the grounds of gender, race, nationality, language, origin, social status, belief, convictions or views, as well as the implementation of the provisions of legal acts of the European Union referred to in the Annex to this Law and of other international legal acts”.* This law specifically notes the *“Duty of Educational Establishments, Other Education Providers as well as Research and Education Establishments to Implement Equal Treatment”*, which states that educational establishments (including HEIs) *“must ensure equal conditions for persons irrespective of gender, race, nationality, language, origin, social status, belief, convictions or views, age, sexual orientation, disability, ethnic origin or religion”* in certain circumstances, including but not limited to admission procedures, granting of scholarships, development and approval of education programs, evaluation of learning achievements.

In **Norway**, the law relating to universities and university colleges specifically references gender equality, stating that *“universities and university colleges must make active, targeted and systematic efforts to ensure gender equality in all categories of employment at the institution”.* Some revisions were adopted in 2022; universities and university colleges were to be considered public bodies

according to the Equality and Discrimination Act. This duty implies that they “*shall in all their activities make active, targeted and systematic efforts to promote equality and prevent discrimination*”. The grounds/dimensions mentioned in the Equality and Discrimination Act are also applicable to universities and university colleges: gender, pregnancy, leave in connection with childbirth or adoption, care responsibilities, ethnicity, religion, belief, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, gender expression, age or combinations of these factors is prohibited. «Ethnicity» includes national origin, descent, skin colour and language.

The Universities and University Colleges Act assigns Boards the responsibility to prevent and stop harassment and sexual harassment. It also addresses individual adaptation to ensure equal educational opportunities for students with disabilities and special needs.

Broadly conceived national/regional law for higher education, research and innovation that address topic of equality, diversity, and inclusion

As with national laws, legislation that focuses on higher education, research and innovation that addresses grounds beyond gender do so by referencing additional grounds. As with sector-specific laws discussed previously, it is not clear how these are implemented in practice and if the protection of multiple grounds is undertaken intersectionally or separately as an additive approach. In those laws to which respondents have referred, there is a strong focus on access to education rather than specific supports to assist the progression and retention of students and/or staff from minority groups in HE or any clear evidence of an intersectional approach. As this pattern emerges, we may draw the conclusion that national laws, which are in turn based on international human rights and EU legislation, must focus on the protection of multiple but separate equality grounds. Given this legal necessity, it appears that the translation of intersectionality into legislation is not entirely possible, beyond referencing the need to take an intersectional approach in the promotion of gender equality (as in the Spanish example). This suggests that there is a legislative imperative to work on multiple equality grounds, which in turn means that there is potential for policy to reflect this and to adopt or encourage an intersectional approach, particularly in instances where countries have already developed gender equality-specific strategies.

For instance in **the Czech Republic**, the Law on Pre-school, Basic, Secondary, Tertiary Professional and Other Education states “*Education shall be based on the principles of that equal access of all citizens of the Czech Republic or nationals of any other European Union Member State to education without any discrimination based on any ground such as race, colour, sex, language, belief or religion, nationality, ethnic or social origin, property, kith or kin, or the health condition or any other status of a citizen*”. While among “*the general goals of education [...] shall be understanding and application of the principle of equality of women and men in society*”, this is broadened out with reference to other goals such as “*the formation of national and state citizenship awareness and respect for the ethnic, national, cultural, language and religious identity of every person*” and “*knowledge of global and European cultural values and traditions, understanding and acquiring principles and rules arising from European integration as a basis for coexistence at national and international levels*”.

In **Ireland**, higher education legislation dictates that one of the functions of the national Higher Education Authority is to promote “equality, diversity and inclusion in higher education” in a number of articles yet does not specifically list what equality grounds are to be the focus of this function.

In **Israel**, the law protects Equal rights regulations for people with disabilities, however, this particular law refers to accessibility adjustments to existing public places that are higher education institutions and the higher education services they provide.

In **Poland**, the Law on Higher Education and Science contains some provisions regarding some dimensions of the topic of equality, diversity, and inclusion, other than gender, including socio-economic status, disability, rehabilitation and the employment of disabled persons, age and foreigners in the system of higher education and science. These provisions mainly relate to access to scholarships or reduced fees to attend higher education.

In **Portugal**, one of the main principles of the Basic Law of the Educational System is that “all Portuguese citizens have the right to education and to culture, according to the Constitutional Law, and the State promotes democratization of education, with a fair and effective equality of opportunities in education access and success”. This law embeds Article no. 13 of the Portuguese Constitution that states that: “All citizens have the same social dignity and are equal before the law” and “No one shall be privileged, favoured, prejudiced, deprived of any right or exempted from any duty on the grounds of ancestry, sex, race, language, territory of origin, religion, political or ideological beliefs, education, economic situation, social condition or sexual orientation.” Again, this law focuses on access to higher education and multiple protected grounds.

Discrimination grounds/ Equality dimensions in policy for HE and R&I

In this section we look closer at policy documents for HE and R&I that include multiple equality dimensions. There were six countries (including both regions of Belgium) with gender equality policies for HE and R&I (Table 1). Among these there were four countries where gender policies for HE and R&I also included other equality dimensions. These countries were Ireland, Belgium (FWB), Croatia and Spain (Table 2, category II). To also include countries that have other documents addressing several dimensions in HE and R&I, we asked for policies where the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion were addressed in more broadly conceived national/ regional policies/ strategies for HE&RI. Countries that have these kinds of documents are Norway, Poland, Austria, Lithuania, Greece, Sweden, and Portugal (Table 2, category IV). By also including this latter group of seven countries, we find that quite a few countries (11) in the sample have policies or other documents for HE and R&I that address several equality dimensions.

Both groups of countries were asked to identify which equality dimensions are addressed in their policy. If we merge results for these two groups of countries, we find that age, socio-economic status, ethnicity, and inequality grounds taken together were most prevalent, mentioned by 7 of 11 respondents. Gender identity and disability were mentioned by 5, while religion and sexual orientation were mentioned by four. LGBTQIA+ was mentioned by the smallest number of respondents.

Figure 3 Equality dimensions in both broadly conceived and specific policies in HE and R&I

Below is a table showing which equality dimensions are mentioned in policies in countries that have a specific gender policy for HE and R&I that includes other dimensions (Group 2 in Table 4) and for the countries where other policies or strategies for the HE and R&I sector that includes other discrimination grounds than gender (Group 1 in Table 4).

In figure 3 we see that age, socio-economic status and ethnicity were most prevalent among the countries that have other policies or strategies for the HE and R&I sector that includes other discrimination grounds than gender. In countries that have a specific gender policy that includes other grounds, the dimension “inequality grounds taken together” is mentioned by Belgium FWB and Ireland, while socio-economic status, and ethnicity are mentioned by Spain and gender identity is mentioned by Croatia.

Figure 4 Comparing equality dimensions in specific gender policies in HE and R&I and broad national/regional policies and strategies for HE and R&I

In this table we show the discrimination grounds/ dimensions that are most common in group 1 and 2 countries.

Table 4 Equality dimensions in different countries

Equality dimension	Group 1 Equality, diversity and inclusion in broad national/regional policies or strategies for HE+RI (5.7)	Group 2 Additional dimensions in national/regional policy on gender equality for HE+RI (5.4)
Age	Austria, Greece, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Sweden	
Disability	Greece, Lithuania, Norway, Portugal, Sweden	
Ethnicity	Austria, Greece, Lithuania, Norway, Portugal, Sweden	Spain
Gender identity	Greece, Lithuania, Portugal, Sweden	Croatia
Inequality grounds (taken together)	Greece, Lithuania, Norway, Portugal, Sweden	Belgium FWB, Ireland
LGBTQIA+	Greece, Portugal, Sweden	
Religion	Greece, Lithuania, Portugal, Sweden	
Sexual orientation	Greece, Lithuania, Portugal, Sweden	
Socio-economic status	Austria, Greece, Lithuania, Norway, Portugal, Sweden	Spain

Countries with HE and R&I policies that include gender and other dimensions (Group 2) mention fewer grounds in their policies than countries with broadly conceived national/regional policies for HE and R&I (Group 1). They refer to three grounds – Ethnicity, Gender identity and Inequality grounds taken together.

Most countries which address equality, diversity and inclusion in broadly conceived national/regional policies/strategies include a high number of equality dimensions, such as Portugal, Sweden and Lithuania. Poland and Norway include fewer dimensions, but Norway has policies that address several equality dimensions taken together.

When we previously looked at *sector level legislation*, only Norway addressed inequality grounds taken together. When we look at countries with broadly conceived policies, Greece, Lithuania, Norway, Portugal, and Sweden refer to this catch-all category.

The texts in the policies, analysed below, give examples, and expand on what can be learned from figure 3 and table 4.

Broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for HE and R&I that address the topic of equality, diversity, and inclusion

Countries that did not have national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in their country were asked if the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion were covered by other broader policies or strategies for HE and R&I. Seven countries provided documentation in relation to this question (AT, EL, LT, NO, PL PT, SE), although in a number of cases the broadly conceived policy only included references to gender equality, rather than to wider equality, diversity and inclusion issues or grounds (AT, EL) and in one instance it was difficult to ascertain how the policy addressed broader equality, diversity and inclusion (PL).

Interestingly, the Austrian example refers to the National Strategy on the Social Dimension in Higher Education, with the concept of “social dimension” referring to equality/diversity more broadly. However, this policy/strategy focuses on equality of access to higher education, as we have seen above in relation to some national laws. The Swedish Discrimination Act, which applies to educational institutions including HEIs, specifies a number of equality grounds that are to be protected: “The purpose of this Act is to combat discrimination and in other ways promote equal rights and opportunities regardless of sex, transgender identity or expression, ethnicity, religion or other belief, disability, sexual orientation or age.”

The two most concrete examples of broadly conceived policies/strategies that address equality, diversity and inclusion are from NO and PT.

In **Norway**, the mandate for the Committee for Gender Balance and Diversity in Research (Kif) states that (our emphasis):

*“The Committee shall support and give recommendations regarding measures that promote the integration of **gender balance and diversity activities** at universities, university colleges and research institutes. The Committee shall seek to raise the overall level of **awareness of issues related to diversity, inclusion and harassment** at higher education and research institutions. This includes **increased knowledge about how gender, social and ethnic background affect critical transitions in a research career; from the path into research to senior-level and leadership positions.**”*

The committee has worked to increase the knowledge base and taken several initiatives, such as data collection and research on ethnic minorities in academia, conferences, and seminars, integrating equality and diversity in the national career strategy and in annual letters of administration to higher education institutions.

The Norwegian Governments Long-term plan for research and higher education 2023–2032 mentions equality and diversity, including indigenous people, national minorities, and other minority groups:

The government has ambitions for more equality, less discrimination and greater diversity. However, the policy area is described as "weak on research" by the Research Council of Norway. The Ministry of Culture and Equality has therefore established a collaboration with the Research Council with the aim of putting forward a cross-sector R&D strategy in 2023. A new report from The Nordic Institute for Studies on Innovation, Research and Education (NIFU) recommends particularly strengthened research into discrimination grounds and forms of discrimination, on which little research has been done until now. The government will prepare and implement a cross-sectoral R&D strategy to strengthen the knowledge base for equality, non-discrimination, and diversity efforts.

In **Portugal**, the National Strategy for Equality and Non-Discrimination 2018-2030, which applies to RPOs and RFOs, considers intersectionality as a transversal issue running across all actions and measures. It states that:

“...a premise in defining measures addressed to disadvantages that occur at the intersection of the sex with other factors of discrimination, including, age, racial and ethnic origin, disability, nationality, sexual orientation, identity and expression of gender, and sexual characteristics. ENIND recognizes, deepens, and prioritize, in all areas, targeted interventions to intersectional disadvantages, such as those inflicted to migrant women belonging to ethnic minorities, refugees, disabled, alone with dependent descendants and elderly.”

As with the **BE-FWB** and **IE** policies mentioned above, this is one of the few national policy documents to explicitly reference intersectionality. However, as above, it remains unclear how this concept is implemented in practice.

Terminology

A starting point in this study is that the field of inclusion and intersectionality is at an initial phase. We have previously identified which equality dimensions in addition to gender are most frequently in use in MS and AC policies and strategies for HE and R&I. When we chose to examine terminology and ask experts at national level¹³ which terms are most frequently used, we wished to use that as an indicator of existing approaches regarding multidimensional equality and intersectionality that could tell us more about the status of inclusive policies in the sample of MS and AC. Rather than asking only about the use of *intersectionality* as a term, we used a list of terms that may indicate the approach or rationale for inclusive policies, i.e., equality, representation, diversity, non-discrimination, inclusiveness and intersectionality.

In figure 4 and table 5 below, a variety of inclusive terminology is identified based on the responses provided. Altogether 11 countries/regions in the two groups responded to the question(s)¹⁴ about

¹³ Respondents who referred to multiple grounds of inequality in their gender policies and broadly based policies and strategies for HE and R&I (Group 1 and 2 in Table 4) were asked to elaborate on the terms used in these documents.

¹⁴ 5.5 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your policy and initiatives, what are the terms most frequently used? And 5.7.2 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your national/ regional policies or strategies, what are the terms most frequently used?

terms most frequently used in policies and initiatives. The most frequently used terms were equity/equality (7), non-discrimination (7) and intersectionality (6). Representation (4) and Inclusive equality (1) were mentioned by the fewest.

Figure 5 Terminology in all policies at HE and R&I level

Table 5 Terminology use in all policies at HE and R&I level

Terms	Group 1 Terminology in broad national/regional policies or strategies for HE+RI (n=7)	Group 2 Terminology in policy on gender equality for HE+RI (n=4)
Diversity	Greece, Norway	Belgium-FW, Croatia, Ireland
Equity/equality	Austria, Greece, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Portugal	Belgium-FW
Gender+ equality	Greece, Portugal, Sweden	Belgium-FW, Croatia
Inclusive equality	Poland	0
Inclusiveness/inclusion ^[1]	Greece, Norway, Portugal	Croatia, Ireland,
Intersectionality	Austria, Greece, Portugal	Belgium-FW, Ireland, Spain
Non-discrimination	Greece, Lithuania, Norway, Portugal, Sweden	Belgium-FW, Croatia
Representation	Austria, Lithuania, Portugal	Belgium-FW

^[1] Israel has a gender equality strategy but does not mention other equality dimensions and is therefore not a part of Group 1 and 2 mentioned above. Israel uses the terms inclusiveness/inclusion in its policy.

When we look separately at countries in group 1 and group 2, group 1 has a wide use of terms related to equality, diversity, and inclusion. The terms equality/equity and non-discrimination are used by 5 out of 7 countries in group 1. Portugal uses equity/equality, gender+ equality, inclusiveness/inclusion, non-discrimination, and representation. Greece uses diversity, gender+ equality, Inclusiveness/inclusion, intersectionality, and non-discrimination. Sweden uses gender+ equality and non-discrimination.

In group 2 Belgium-FW uses all terms but inclusiveness/inclusion. Croatia uses diversity, gender+ equality and non-discrimination, while Ireland uses diversity, inclusiveness/inclusion and intersectionality, and Spain only intersectionality. The figure and table can help us single out countries using a wide range of multidimensional or intersectional terminology. However, they are not sufficient to indicate whether a wider range of inclusive/intersectional terms in policy texts are a push-factor for an expanded equality agenda in the HE and R&I sector. The text analysis of policy documents from group 1 and group 2 in chapter 5.2 may provide a broader picture of the use of terms, and what it implies for how specific countries are about multidimensional or intersectional aspects in their policies.

In Chapter 2 Policy background we referred to how EU policy papers¹⁵ increasingly use terminology such as inclusion, diversity, and intersectionality where different discrimination grounds such as ethnicity, religion, social background, and disability are identified. This means that national authorities in MS and ACs increasingly meet expectations about formulating national policy for HE and R&I using inclusive terminology in keeping with EU-policy in this area.

Terminology used in policies that cover grounds of inequality other than gender

Notably, only four countries provided further information in relation to this, BE-FWB, ES, IE, HR. While it was hard to ascertain how the Croatian National Policy for Gender Equality discussed equality grounds beyond gender, the remaining 3 respondents made clear reference to the concept of intersectionality.

As discussed above, **Spanish** law explicitly notes the need to take an intersectional approach in the promotion of a gender perspective in scientific and technical research, as well as containing a requirement that intersectionality is integrated into the development of gender equality policies. However, it was not clear from the documentation provided how the use of the term “intersectionality” in legislation has translated into policy and practice. It may be useful to investigate further how this legal requirement is implemented in practice.

Ministry of the **Wallonia-Brussels** Federation reports that “intersectionality” is referenced in the introduction and foreword parts of the *Plan Droits des femmes*. Specifically, in the foreword to the plan, the Minister for Children, Health, Culture, Media and Women's Rights notes that its methodology is based on:

“two important assumptions: that of citizen participation as the keystone of political legitimacy, and that of intersectionality as a sine qua none of inclusive feminist politics. Far from being limited to the enumeration, in this document, of the relationships of domination that intersect, intersectionality will be deployed in the working methods. In order to avoid limiting the actions implemented to the situated point of view of the majority social groups, I will ensure that the composition of the mechanisms intended to ensure the monitoring of this plan represents the diversity of society and takes into account the different relations of structural domination at

¹⁵ The EU gender equality strategy (Union of Equality) stated that the strategy would use intersectionality as a cross-cutting principle throughout (A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 p 2). See also The Communication “A new ERA for Research and Innovation” and The Council Conclusions on the New European Research Area (ERA) in December 2020 (Approaches to inclusive gender equality in research and innovation, EU 2022).

work to better unravel them. In other words, I will ensure that this women's rights plan defends, in words and in deeds, the rights of all women, without exception.”

Further, this Plan goes on to offer a definition of intersectionality as follows:

“Created in 1989 by American law professor Kimberlé Crenshaw, the concept of intersectionality designates the intertwining of relations of domination based in particular on sex, “race” (understood as a social construction) or social class. These forms of oppression do not add up but give rise to specific experiences for women belonging to minority social groups (racialized, poor, lesbian, disabled women, etc.).”

The Plan clearly states that in addition to the concrete measures that it outlines, the ultimate goal is to strengthen gender mainstreaming in all public institutions and to do so taking an intersectional approach:

“Beyond the precise and concrete measures presented in this plan, the intention is to strengthen the dynamic of gender mainstreaming in all the institutions active in the competences of the FWB, while integrating it in an intersectional perspective.”

Finally, one of the actions in the plan, which is focused on training for teachers and educational staff, notes that this training will aim in particular to integrate the importance of social and gender diversity and to deconstruct gender stereotypes according to an intersectional reading grid. The *Plan Droits des femmes* is one of the few examples of a national policy/action plan that clearly articulates an intersectional perspective in gender equality work. Nonetheless, further research is needed on how this concept has been applied in practice.

In our sample, the most comprehensive example of efforts to integrate an intersectional approach in national policy relating to higher education/R&I comes from **Ireland**. The *2nd HEA National Review of Gender Equality in Irish Higher Education Institutions* includes a chapter on Intersectionality as a new focus in Irish equality policy, as well as a key recommendation on Intersectionality:

“The advancement of gender equality is dependent on progress on a range of factors including race equality, precarious employment, and family status and disability equalities. Accordingly, HEIs should develop EDI strategies and action plans that seek to effect change in a way that centralises an intersectional approach to equality issues, within a 3–4-year timeframe.”

A national report that analysed a national survey on Race Equality in the Higher Education Sector referenced intersectionality as an issue mentioned by survey respondents as follows:

“Intersectionality was another issue raised by people coming from both ethnic minority and White Irish backgrounds, with gender being seen as a further obstacle to promotion/career progression. This suggests that in order to better understand experiences of ethnic minority groups in HEIs we need to address the intersections of gender, race/ethnicity, nationality and class dimensions.”

This led to the report's authors recommending the introduction of “Mandatory antiracism training for staff at all levels with an emphasis on intersectionality” in all Irish HEIs. More recently, the Irish Higher Education Authority has published *Anti-Racism Principles for Irish Higher Education Institutions*¹⁶ which specifically address the concept of intersectionality. The document includes both principles and

¹⁶ <https://hea.ie/assets/uploads/2022/03/Anti-Racism-Principles-for-Irish-Higher-Education-Institutions.pdf>

commitments which Irish HEIs are requested to endorse. Intersectionality is referenced twice as part of these, as follows:

“Principle 6: The complex nature of the intersection of race inequality with other characteristics protected under Irish equality legislation must be taken into account when developing anti-racism actions and policies.”

“Commitment 5: We will adopt an intersectional and intercultural approach when developing anti-racism actions and policies.”

Like BE-FWB, this Irish policy models its understanding of intersectionality on the concept first discussed by Kimberlé Crenshaw (see Chapter 3).

As with the documents provided by respondents in relation to national/regional laws, these policy documents do not fully articulate how the recommendation requirement to take an intersectional approach to equality work has been implemented in practice. While the use of the term intersectionality and its meaning are clearer in the BE-FWB and IE policy documents, the use of an intersectional approach is not evidenced. This points to the fact that while national authorities can set requirements for RPOs and RFOs to approach gender equality from an intersectional perspective, it is perhaps only possible to see how this is translated into practice through analysis of institutional GEPs and their implementation.

It seems that at this stage, intersectional approaches are still more developed in research and in the work of anti-discrimination bodies regarding individual complaints than at a system level. Intersectional approaches are more developed on a theoretical level rather than in practice. Further, while we see some evidence of intersectionality being taken into account in cases of research methods or individual complaints, it is yet to be embedded as a system-level approach.

With the background of increased expectations from the EU and a tentative hypothesis that finding a wide range of good practices was unlikely at this stage, we were interested in obstacles, and the need for initiatives and knowledge to raise intersectional perspectives on the agenda.

What may help to lift the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the policy agenda?

This section gives an overview of initiatives and knowledge that may help to lift the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the policy agenda within ministries at national level and the European Research Area. Altogether 13 out of 15 respondents answered this question.

Figure 6 Initiatives and knowledge needed ¹⁷

In figure 6 we see that the measures mentioned by most respondents were Mutual learning initiatives (10), the need to commission research (9) and financial incentives and support. Others mentioned advanced legal framework at national level and clear guidelines from the EC (7).

When looking at the country list of the 13 respondents crossed with types of initiatives (table 6), most countries have responded to at least two alternatives, Norway and Belgium FWB responded to five. If we look at the relatively high response per variable in the questionnaire, responses indicate the need for multiple measures to raise intersectional perspectives in national policies.

Table 6 Initiatives/knowledge needed

Initiatives/knowledge needed	Responses from 13 national/regional respondents
Mutual learning initiatives	Austria, Belgium FWB, Croatia, Denmark, Ireland, Israel, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain
Research commissioned	Belgium FWB, Croatia, Ireland, Israel, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Spain, Sweden
Financial incentives/support	Austria, Belgium FWB, Croatia, Czech Republic, Israel, Lithuania, Norway, Portugal
Advanced legal framework	Austria, Belgium FWB, Czech Republic, Israel, Norway, Spain, Sweden
Clear guidelines from the EC	Austria, Belgium FWB, Israel, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Spain
Don't know (can be removed)	Lithuania, Belgium Flanders

¹⁷ 5.10 What initiatives and knowledge are needed to lift the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the policy agenda at your ministry and on the policy agenda in the European Research Area?

There were several additional comments under “other” (what other initiatives and knowledge is needed). One was a supplementary comment to the suggested initiatives in the questionnaire on *financial incentives and support*, “there is a need for incentives and support, but not necessarily financial (thus not ticked the box)”. On *Clear guidelines from the EC*, one respondent remarked there is a need for clear guidelines at national level, rather than at the EC level.

There were also comments on alternatives not included in the questionnaire. Two respondents mentioned the need for data collection, “the need for data and monitoring”, and “the development of disaggregated data in HEIs on other dimensions than gender, to build interest and relevance for policymaking on intersecting challenges”. Lack of disaggregated data was also identified as an obstacle to lifting an intersectional approach in a few countries (see Table 7 Obstacles).

Finally, one respondent addressed the challenges of collaboration and a charged political context in Central Europe. “There are separate agendas for different interest groups for different “grounds”- and it is demanding to coordinate/interact (e.g., LGBT+, Roma, immigrant issues)”. The same respondent also said that “gender – in this context reduced to equality of women and men - is already a difficult topic to address. Adding other aspects that are politically charged (LGBTQ+, gender identity, ethnicity), can ultimately worsen the position of the gender equality agenda”. These are important contextual factors which also show the variation in starting point for different countries; some have difficulty lifting gender equality while other countries already have several dimensions included in policy and active measures.

What helps and what hinders implementation of inclusive/intersectional measures

Work with equality and non-discrimination may meet resistance in many countries, and it is therefore natural to try to identify possible obstacles. Intersectional perspectives at policy level have not been developed as much as in the legal sphere and in research. Given these considerations we asked respondents about what *obstacles* are met when developing a policy including an intersectional approach¹⁸ and what *national measures exist* to support the implementation of inclusive/ intersectional policies in research. We chose to address these questions to authorities that already have multidimensional policies.

In the following we describe the responses to these questions. Despite the few responses received, which makes it hard to generalise, this section can at least provide an overview of the status in the few countries that responded.

Obstacles – an interesting question with limited response

Only the countries with a specific gender equality policy for higher education/ research answered this question. Out of six respondents from countries that have a gender equality policy for HE and R&I, four countries identified obstacles in developing an intersectional approach. These countries were Ireland, Croatia, Israel, and Belgium.¹⁹ When considering where we might find relevant experiences, all four countries might be of interest. It is worth noting that Belgium FWB, that included many dimensions in its policy, also reports multiple obstacles.

¹⁸ 5.8 Has your ministry or any other relevant national/regional authority faced any of the following obstacles in developing a policy including an intersectional approach?

¹⁹ In comparison, in the benchmark for research funding organisations, all 19 RFOs that had gender equality policies were asked about obstacles.

Table 7 Obstacles

Country/region	Belgium-FWB	Croatia	Ireland	Israel
No unified understanding of concepts		✓	✓	
Lack of human resources		✓	✓	
Lack of data	✓			✓
Lack of national policy	✓			
Uncertain of terminology	✓	✓	✓	
Lack of research-based knowledge	✓	✓		
Lack of interest/ relevance	✓			
Gender is itself a struggle	✓			✓
Lack of economic resources	✓		✓	
Management resistance	✓			

Supportive measures

We asked countries with gender equality policies in higher education if they have national measures to support the implementation of inclusive/ intersectional policies in research.²⁰ Israel, Ireland, and Belgium (both regions) have national measures to support the implementation of inclusive/intersectional policies. As in the previous section on obstacles, there are too few responses to draw any general conclusions. The use of supportive measures for policy implementation may be worth exploring when more countries develop relevant multidimensional and intersectional policies in the HE and R&I sector.

Table 8 Supportive measures

	Reporting on gender balance indicators	Reporting other grounds of inequality	National conferences	Financial incentives	Advisory centres for gender equality	National committees	National awareness-raising campaigns
Israel	✓			✓		✓	
Ireland	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Belgium-FWB	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
Belgium-FWB	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓

In this chapter, we have identified legislation and policies for HE and R&I that include more grounds than gender. For the sample of 15 countries/ regions, the survey identified a good legal and policy framework on anti-discrimination and equal opportunity that was partly mirrored when including multidimensional laws and policies (both sector specific and broadly conceived) for HE and R&I. When

²⁰ 5.9 Do you have national measures to support the implementation of inclusive/ intersectional policies in research? If yes, please tick all that apply.

identifying the dimensions included in the multidimensional laws and policies, most dimensions were included. Some dimensions, like age, socio-economic status, ethnicity, and inequality grounds taken together, were those that were included most often. At policy level we found fewer countries with sector-specific multidimensional policies, and they also included fewer dimensions than those with broadly conceived policies for HE and R&I that more countries had and that included more dimensions.

By analysing the legal and policy documents provided by the respondents, we detected that although many respondents answered in the survey that they include many equality dimensions in their legal and policy documents, there were few examples in the texts attached where these dimensions were discussed. In the texts where they were discussed they were used as statements and in an additive fashion. There were few examples of intersectional approach when discussing several equality dimensions.

5.2. Research Funding Organisations

5.2.1. An overview of the findings in the survey and document analysis

Key Findings

- 19 out of 20 respondents answered that the RFO had a dedicated gender equality policy.
- 14 RFOs answered that their gender equality policies also include other equality dimensions.
- The number of RFOs (14) with several equality dimensions indicates that there is a good foundation for developing an intersectional approach in policies.
- It appears that the discussion on intersectionality and inclusiveness is gaining traction in RFO policies although there are few examples of how they are translated into practice.
- There are traces of intersectional thinking, but no comprehensive examples of a methodology or best practices of systemic intersectional policies.
- RFOs with policies including more dimensions than gender mostly refer to these dimensions in connection with statements of priorities and not practice.
- The obstacles mentioned in this benchmark can be used positively to develop the work with a more inclusive and intersectional approach over time, an approach which should be supported and facilitated by national level policy.
- A unified understanding of concepts is needed.
- An underlying principle in policy development in general, but particularly in the HE and R&I sector, is that change should be data, research and evidence driven.

In this section we present the results from the part of the benchmarking survey undertaken in 2022 mapping research funding organisations (RFO) in European countries. Representatives from 20 RFOs from 16 countries have responded to this benchmark. The results presented in this chapter reflect the replies to the part of the benchmark where the purpose was to identify which RFOs have policies that are expanded to more equality dimensions than gender and whether intersectional perspectives are addressed in their respective policies. The survey provides information about the most common equality dimensions and terminology included in RFOs equality policies. Respondents also give input on what initiatives and knowledge are needed to lift the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the policy agenda.

This analysis builds on multiple choice responses to the benchmark questionnaire, supplemented by answers to open questions and quotes from policy documents supplied by respondents.²¹

Figure 7 Overview RFOs

As illustrated above in Figure 7, 20 research funding organisations (RFOs) from 17 countries responded to the survey. The results presented in this section cover only the 19 RFOs with a gender equality policy²². Given the focus on additional equality dimensions in gender equality policies, the illustration also shows how many RFOs have additional dimensions in their policies.

Table 9 Respondents

Country	Gender policy with additional equality dimensions?	Acronym	Research funding organisation
Belgium- FWB	No	F.R.S.-FNRS	Fund for scientific research and the abbreviation is F.R.S.-FNRS
Belgium-Flanders	Yes	FWO	Research Foundation - Flanders (FWO)

²¹ In order to make sure that all relevant documents pertaining to inclusive policies were supplied by the sample of RFOs, the RFOs were asked if the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion was addressed in more broadly conceived policies and strategies (e.g., strategic plans, mission statement). No RFOs supplied such documents.

²² One RFO (from Bulgaria) was not included, because it did not have a gender policy, and did not respond to most questions in this work package.

Cyprus	Yes	RIF	Research and Innovation Foundation
Czech Republic	Yes	TACR	Technology Agency of the Czech Republic
Denmark	No	DFF	Independent Research Fund Denmark, DFF
Estonia	No	ETAG	Estonian Research Council
Ireland	No	IRC	Irish Research Council (through beneficiary HEA)
Italy	Yes	FRRB	Regional Foundation for Biomedical Research
Lithuania	Yes	RCL	Research Council of Lithuania
Malta	Yes	MCST	Malta Council for Science and Technology, MCST
Norway	Yes	RCN	Research Council of Norway
Poland	Yes	NCRD	National Centre for Research and Development
Poland	Yes	NCN	National Science Centre
Portugal	Yes	FCT	Foundation for Science and Technology
Romania	No	UEFISCDI	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding
Spain	Yes	AEI	State Research Agency
Sweden	Yes	Vinnova	Vinnova Swedish Agency for Innovation Systems
Sweden	Yes	Forte	Forte, Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare
Turkey	Yes	TÜBİTAK	The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey

What is meant by policies – and how is equality work supported in RFOs?

As a first step in this benchmark on intersectionality we identified which RFOs that include more equality dimensions than gender in their Gender Equality Policies as this is a precondition for having an inclusive or intersectional approach in a policy.

For this benchmark, policies are defined as documents officially adopted by the governing body of the organisation. The responses show that gender equality policies take different forms across the responding RFOs. The documents provided by the respondents include a variety of documents including gender equality plans, plans for gender mainstreaming, equal opportunity policies or ethics codes.

19 respondents answered that the RFO had a dedicated gender equality policy – and that they have a unit/person responsible for implementing the policy.²³

Most of the RFOs' gender policies were adopted between 2018-22. While some refer to a recent revision of existing policies that were adopted earlier, others refer only to their current policy without indicating whether it is an older policy that is revised or a new one.

²³ Some have a team, a working group or a person who is a coordinator or equality officer. Their placement varies between the Innovation Department, the Presidency/Board of Directors, Human Resources /Personnel Unit or the Analysis Department.

Equality dimensions addressed in RFO policies

All respondents were asked whether their gender equality policies also include other equality dimensions. Altogether 14 RFOs mentioned at least one, with the majority noting more than one dimension in addition to gender²⁴. Only five of the nineteen answered “none” to this question.

Figure 8 Dimensions included in multidimensional gender equality policies (RFOs)

In the figure we see that disability (10), gender identity (9) and age (9) are most frequently mentioned. Other dimensions mentioned are ethnicity (8), religion (7) sexual orientation (7) and socio-economic status. Least mentioned are LGBTQIA+ and inequality grounds taken together with 5 each respectively.

Another way of looking at the dimensions mentioned by RFOs is by grouping together interlinked dimensions; We can see that categories associated with gender/sexual identity (21) and ethnicity/religion (15) are the second most common dimensions mentioned. Disability, age, and inequality grounds taken together²⁵ are mentioned by fewer.

There are variations between RFOs in this survey. The table below provides detail about the equality dimensions covered by the individual RFOs.

²⁴ There was no specification regarding where these equality dimensions are applied in the question and responses to this question. See the analysis of policy documents for further elaboration.

²⁵ After going through the responses, we realize that the category “Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)” is ambiguous: It can be perceived as an acknowledgment of all protected grounds in national antidiscrimination laws or an integrated or inclusive approach of many dimensions. This is not clear without delving into how the separate dimensions and their interaction are understood in policies.

Table 10 Variations in the use of dimensions between RFOs

Included dimensions	Respondents
Age	FWO Belgium-Flanders, TACR Czech Republic, FRRB Italy, MCST Malta, NCN Poland, FCT Portugal, Forte Sweden, Vinnova Sweden, TÜBITAK Turkey
Disability	FWO Belgium-Flanders, TACR Czech Republic, FRRB Italy, MCST Malta, NCN Poland, FCT Portugal, AEI Spain, Forte Sweden, Vinnova Sweden, TÜBITAK Turkey
Ethnicity	FWO Belgium-Flanders, TACR Czech Republic, FRRB Italy, MCST Malta, FCT Portugal, Forte Sweden, Vinnova Sweden, TÜBITAK Turkey
Gender identity	FWO Belgium-Flanders, RIF Cyprus, TACR Czech Republic, FRRB Italy, RCL Lithuania, MCST Malta, NCN Poland, Forte Sweden, Vinnova Sweden
Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)	RCL Lithuania, RCN Norway, FCT Portugal, Forte Sweden, Vinnova Sweden
LGBTQIA+	TACR Czech Republic, MCST Malta, NCN Poland, Forte Sweden, Vinnova Sweden
Religion	TACR Czech Republic, FRRB Italy, MCST Malta, FCT Portugal, Forte Sweden, Vinnova Sweden, TÜBITAK Turkey
Sexual orientation	TACR Czech Republic, FRRB Italy, MCST Malta, NCN Poland, FCT Portugal, Forte Sweden, Vinnova Sweden
Socio-economic status	MCST Malta, NCRD Poland, FCT Portugal, Forte Sweden, Vinnova Sweden, TÜBITAK Turkey
None	FRS Belgium-FWB, DFF Denmark, ETAG Estonia, IRC Ireland, UEFISCDI Romania

The respondents were also asked to mention whether they include “other” discrimination grounds than those mentioned in the questionnaire. Portuguese FCT mentions that they also include political and ideological convictions and union affiliation in their policy.

The number of RFOs with several equality dimensions indicates that there is a good foundation for developing an intersectional approach in policies. This will be investigated further in the analysis of the text excerpts provided us.

Terminology

A starting point in this study is that the field of inclusion and intersectionality is at an initial phase. Above we have identified which equality dimensions in addition to gender are most frequently addressed by RFOs in their policies. When we ask RFO representatives about which terms are most frequently used, we wish to use that as an indicator of existing approaches on multidimensional equality. Rather than asking only about the use of intersectionality, we used a list of terms that may indicate the approach or rationale for inclusive policies, i.e., equity/equality, representation, diversity, non-discrimination, inclusiveness, and intersectionality. Figure 9 below gives an overall picture of the most common terms used in gender policy documents in RFOs and show us a great variation.

Figure 9 There is a large variation in the use of terminology

The figure indicates that equity/equality are the most prevalent terms mentioned in the RFO policies. Other commonly used terms are non-discrimination (8), inclusiveness/inclusion (7), diversity (7) and gender+ equality (7). Representation, inclusive equity/equality, intersectionality, and multiple discrimination are least mentioned by respondents. The two most prevalent terms equity/equality and non-discrimination may be linked with a greater emphasis on gender equality in RFOs across Europe lately, or a reflection of national obligations in keeping with equality and discrimination laws.

Table 11 Use of terminology in RFOs

Terminology	Respondents
Diversity	FWO Belgium-Flanders, ETAG Estonia, MCST Malta, RCN Norway, NCN Poland, Forte Sweden, TÜBITAK Turkey
Equity/equality	FWO Belgium-Flanders, TACR Czech Republic, DFF Denmark, ETAG Estonia, FRRB Italy, RCL Lithuania, MCST Malta, NCN Poland, NCRD Poland, FCT Portugal
Gender+ equality	RIF Cyprus, FRRB Italy, RCL Lithuania, MCST Malta, NCRD Poland, NCN Poland, Vinnova Sweden
Inclusive equality	RCL Lithuania, RCN Norway, TÜBITAK Turkey
Inclusiveness/inclusion	MCST Malta, RCN Norway, NCN Poland, AEI Spain, Forte Sweden, Forte Sweden, TÜBITAK Turkey
Intersectionality	RCL Lithuania, Vinnova Sweden
Multiple discrimination	Forte Sweden
Non-discrimination	ETAG Estonia, FRRB Italy, RCL Lithuania, RCN Norway, NCN Poland, FCT Portugal, UEFISCDI Romania, Forte Sweden
Representation	ETAG Estonia, RCL Lithuania, MCST Malta, NCN Poland, NCRD Poland

Only two RFOs mention intersectionality. However, there are several other terms used which we can consider to be associated with or lend themselves to an intersectional approach, such as multiple discrimination, gender equality+ and inclusive equality. That may be taken to mean that the discussion

on intersectionality and inclusiveness is gaining traction in RFO policies. However, there is still little direct reference to intersectionality in these policies. In the following section, we discuss some examples of texts provided by the respondents.

How are equality dimensions addressed in RFO policies?

In the sample of 19 RFOs, 14 RFOs indicated that their gender policy included more discrimination grounds (see Table 9 Respondents). The five organisations that answered that they did not have a gender policy with additional equality dimensions²⁶ were asked if the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion were addressed in more broadly conceived policies and strategies. None of these RFOs had such documents and are therefore not included in this analysis. The 14 RFOs with gender policies including other equality dimensions were asked to specify relevant sections in their document to exemplify this. Some RFOs only included text excerpts, while others attached texts and documents where more equality dimensions were mentioned. To find out in what way the dimensions were described and translated into practice, all documents and text excerpts were studied. In addition, all the attached documents were reviewed to cross-check what was provided in the textual responses to the survey and to find out if there were other sections of relevance in the documents. To help us find passages of relevance we searched by using the terms intersectionality, diversity, age, disability, ethnicity, identity, and religion. Some of the attached RFO policies were gender equality plans where there was no mention of other discrimination grounds than gender. These policies are therefore not included as they did not provide us with information about how multiple dimensions are addressed. These RFOs are from Belgium FWB, Denmark, Estonia, Ireland, and Romania.

The responses in this part of the survey are a sample of some RFOs' inclusive strategies in European MS and AC. The answers are highly dependent on the responding RFOs. Some countries have many RFOs while others have only one RFO mainly responsible for funding research in their country. In this sample of cases most RFOs are at national level, but some RFOs are regional or an RFO within one discipline is represented (e.g., Italy). The presentation below is therefore an analysis of some European RFOs inclusive policies and not a general description of all European RFOs inclusive work.

How multiple grounds are addressed in the policies.

A general finding emerging from the examination of the attached documents of the 14 RFOs, is that the identified equality dimensions in each RFO are used in connection with statements of priorities of the RFOs where inclusion and having a focus on more than gender is of importance. There are few examples of how multiple grounds are addressed in practice which was also a major finding from the analysis of national laws and policies. The ways in which multiple grounds are addressed include:

- Diversity in statements of priorities
- Diversity, inclusiveness, and value to society
- Diversity to attract and retain talent – increase competitiveness.

There were a few examples of intersectional measures in evidence, but some promising practices are emerging. These are outlined at the end of the section.

Diversity in statements of priorities

Impartiality and non-discrimination: An example from Italy

²⁶ FRS Belgium-FWB, DFF Denmark, ETAG Estonia, IRC Ireland, UEFISCDI Romania

In the Fondazione Regionale per la Ricerca Biomedica (It) Ethics' code it is for example stated *"Fondazione Regionale per la Ricerca Biomedica (FRRB) considers impartiality to be a most important value in any and all of the Foundation's internal and external relations. For this reason, the Foundation rejects and punishes all discriminations with regard to age, sex, sexual attitudes, state of health, race, nationality, political opinions and religious beliefs of all those with whom it comes into contact"* (6. Safeguarding of Human Resources www.frrb_ethics_code_2019.pdf).

Similar statements and listing of several equality dimensions can be found in policies from FORTE (Se), Research Council of Norway (NO), Research Council of Lithuania (LT) and FCT (PT). These are mostly statements on how these RFOs, as organizations and a workplace, should act towards their employees and where several discrimination grounds are listed. This is an excerpt from FORTE's Policy for equal rights: *"Forte is a workplace free from discrimination and harassment and is an organization where employees are treated with respect and consideration. At Forte, employees have equal rights and opportunities regardless of gender, gender identity or expression, ethnicity, belief, disability, sexual orientation, or age. The organization is structured in a way that is inclusive for employees, regardless of background"* ([Policy för lika rättigheter och möjligheter - Forte](#)).

Diversity, inclusiveness, and value to society

In the gender policies for the Research Council of Norway and the Research Council of Lithuania gender is mentioned together with diversity as statements on what gender and diversity is adding to science, the research community, and the society in general. It is stated in this way by the Research Council of Lithuania: *"Gender balance and diversity in the science and research community, as well as an inclusion of the gender perspective in research and innovation development (R&D) projects, are important factors in generating added value to society as a whole"* (Guidance on gender equality of the research council of Lithuania p.1).

In the Research Council of Norway's Policy for gender balance and gender perspectives in research and innovation this is also stated, but also justified, with a more heterogenous and changing society that calls for more diverse approach. *"The world is changing and becoming more diverse. As migration increases and society in general grows more heterogeneous, gender and diversity issues are more often treated as two sides of the same coin. Although this policy specifically applies to gender balance and gender perspectives, several of the measures here will have the important effect of promoting diversity in a broader sense as well. We will also be working to expand knowledge about diversity"* ([nfr_gender_policy_orig.pdf \(forskningsradet.no\)](#)).

These declarations or statements, though not specifying how they will be translated into practice, provide a rationale for the inclusion of diversity with what it adds to science and society and that the RFOs have to have a more inclusive approach in order to meet a more heterogenous and changing society. The Policy from the Research Council of Norway mentions a need to expand knowledge about diversity in the future.

The Research Council's policy instruments seek to encourage institutions to implement researcher recruitment and career development processes that promote gender balance and diversity.

... Gender and diversity perspectives must be carefully assessed and integrated where relevant.

Diversity (and inclusion)

The Research Council's diversity work forms an integrated part of collaboration between the management and the employee representatives. However, the whole organisation must contribute in order to succeed with the diversity and inclusion efforts. Emphasis is placed on broad involvement in

equality work by employees throughout the organisation through e.g., workshops and lectures. The work also includes obtaining knowledge about how to make strategic efforts in diversity. Our ambition is to comply with the Norwegian standard for diversity management as far as possible.

The excerpts above partly speak of the society at large, partly address inclusion/diversity related to employees within the RFO.

The term diversity is often used to signify that more dimensions than gender are in question. There is, however, no broader discussion of what diversity means and what it includes in terms of equality dimensions. From the excerpts the use of diversity in addition to gender does not commit the RFOs to take any active measures on how to include and lift intersections of equality dimension within the organisation or towards HE and R&I sector. When replying to what needs to be done to lift the intersection of gender with other dimensions to the RFOs policy agenda Vinnova (SE) replies “a deeper understanding of the concepts, for example diversity, [which] is foremost understood as ethnicity only, distinction of the concept diversity in terms of people (teams), ideas, innovative solutions etc.”

Diversity to attract and retain talent – increase competitiveness.

In the gender strategy for the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic (TACR) [gender_policy.pdf \(tacr.cz\)](#) several discrimination grounds are mentioned in the introduction as a statement like for the RFOs mentioned above: *“The TACR gender policy is based on established approaches in EU countries, where anti-discrimination principles enhance the competitiveness of their respective countries, meaning they can develop, attract and retain the best talent regardless of age, gender, religion, sexual orientation or origin.”* In this policy, having anti-discrimination policies are connected to competitiveness and presented as an instrument to develop, attract, and retain the best talent regardless of diversity background. It is also stated in this document that *“TACR considers diversity in research teams to be a competitive advantage and perceives its responsibility for the promotion of gender equality and diversity in research, development and innovation in the Czech Republic.”*

A few examples of measures

Monitoring survey in TACR

In the Gender Equality Plan 2022-2025 for the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic (TACR) several axes of inequality are listed, but in connection with a measure including several discrimination grounds. This measure is identified as a monitoring exercise among TACR’s employees. It is formulated in this way: *“Monitor perceptions of gender culture and equal opportunities in relation to gender, age, ethnicity, disability, and other potentially disadvantaging characteristics in the organization”* (p. 7). The survey is also referred to in another part of the GEP (p. 19), where also sexual orientation and religion are included. This measure, where perceptions of gender culture and equal opportunities were to be monitored in relation to several discrimination grounds, was for internal use among employees in the Technology Agency for the Czech Republic. Although we do not have information of whether these discrimination grounds were analysed separately or together, it shows an understanding of the importance of looking at different equality dimensions when focusing on gender culture and equal opportunities in the organization ([1662643903_GEP_FINAL.pdf \(tacr.cz\)](#)).

Vinnova’s EDI-plan: 4 steps to promote equality diversity and inclusion

Vinnova’s non-public EDI-plan (only available on their intra-net) informs about a change in legislation in 2017 that has changed their approach to diversity from a mere plan to initiating active measures. The new legislation now expects that *“employers must now continuously conduct and document their*

work with active measures in four steps. The purpose of the work is to prevent discrimination and work for equal rights and opportunities regardless of gender, gender identity or expression, ethnic affiliation, religion or other belief, functional variation, sexual orientation or age in five areas; working conditions, regulations and practices on wages and other terms of employment, recruitment and promotion, training and other skills development and opportunities to combine work and parenthood. Vinnova works actively to promote equality, diversity and inclusion within these areas". In Vinnova's gender mainstreaming plan 2022-2025 ([Microsoft Word - 2021-01628 Vinnovas handlingsplan för jämställdhetsintegrering 2022-2025](#)) it is identified as a new need for development to "Develop Vinnova's ability to work to ensure that granted projects contribute to increased equality through intersectional and inclusive measures when relevant" (p. 7).

The examples from Vinnova, show us that a change in legislation has made Vinnova, as an employer, initiate inclusive active measures. In addition, Vinnova will work to ensure that their granted projects have intersectional and inclusive measures. These are examples of a move towards more inclusion for Vinnova as an employer and as a research funder.

FWO: Considering monitoring applicant nationality

There was scattered use of different discrimination grounds in provided documents from Belgium (Flanders) and Portugal, but no firm inclusive policy. In Belgian Research Foundation - Flanders (FWO) Gender Equality Plan it is mentioned under 1.1.3 Data collection and monitoring that "*The FWO is exploring the possibilities of gaining an insight into the ethnicity/nationality of the applicants, within the boundaries of relevant legislation and regulations in the field of privacy, GDPR, etc.*"

AIE Spain: Social inclusion and disability considered together with gender

The templates regarding the evaluation of the specific criterion "Social and economic impact" of the projects states the following: "*The dissemination of the results to society and open access will be considered. When relevant, the inclusion of the gender dimension in the research proposal and/or the impact on the field of disability and other areas of social inclusion will be also considered [...]*" This is an example of a measure with an external focus (that is directed towards applicants) regarding the content of research.

Many RFOs have moved forward in their thinking on gender equality over time, supported to some extent by EU and national guidelines, research and incentives. This work is not by any means complete, but it has been going on for much longer than the more recent focus on multidimensional and intersectional equality/inclusion efforts.

In this section, we have seen examples of a variety of rationales for inclusion and diversity. We also found some examples of possible measures, such as surveys within RFOs or monitoring ethnicity/nationality of applications. There are traces of intersectional thinking, but no comprehensive examples of a methodology or best practices of systemic intersectional policies.

This leads to a new question in this benchmark study; Why is the situation as it is? Which factors are barriers in developing a broader, more inclusive policy agenda. This brings us to questions respondents have answered regarding obstacles.

Obstacles

In the following, we have asked respondents to indicate what obstacles they have identified in developing a policy including an intersectional approach.²⁷

Figure 10 Obstacles

The figure summarises findings based on possible obstacles on a predefined list. The lack of unified understanding of concepts was the obstacle mentioned by the highest number of respondents (13), followed by the lack of disaggregated data (10) and the lack of human resources (10). Other obstacles mentioned were the lack of national policy (9), lack of research (8), uncertain(ly) about terminology (8) and lack of interest. The last options (economic resources, the struggle to expand beyond gender equality and resistance at management level) had fewer responses but are still notable.

Table 12 Obstacles identified by RFOs

Obstacle	Respondents
Gender equality is a struggle	TACR Czech Republic, DFF Denmark, ETAG Estonia, IRC Ireland, UEFISCDI Romania, Vinnova Sweden
Lack of disaggregated data	TACR Czech Republic, ETAG Estonia, IRC Ireland, RCL Lithuania, RCN Norway, UEFISCDI Romania, AEI Spain, Forte Sweden, Vinnova Sweden, TÜBITAK Turkey
Lack of economic resources	ETAG Estonia, FRRB Italy, RCL Lithuania, MCST Malta, NCRD Poland, UEFISCDI Romania

²⁷ 4.5 Has your RFO faced any of the following obstacles in developing a policy including an intersectional approach?

Lack of human resources	RIF Cyprus, ETAG Estonia, IRC Ireland, FRRB Italy, RCL Lithuania, MCST Malta, NCRD Poland, FCT Portugal UEFISCDI Romania, TÜBITAK Turkey
Lack of interest	RIF Cyprus, TACR Czech Republic, ETAG Estonia, RCL Lithuania, NCRD Poland, UEFISCDI Romania, TÜBITAK Turkey
Lack of national policy	RIF Cyprus, TACR Czech Republic, ETAG Estonia, FRRB Italy, RCL Lithuania, RCN Norway, UEFISCDI Romania, AEI Spain, TÜBITAK Turkey
Lack of research	RIF Cyprus, ETAG Estonia, RCL Lithuania, MCST Malta RCN Norway, NCRD Poland, UEFISCDI Romania, AEI Spain
Lack of unified understanding of concepts	Belgium (Flanders), RIF Cyprus, IRC Ireland, FRRB Italy, RCN Norway, Poland NSC, AEI Spain, ETAG Estonia, NCRD Poland, FCT Portugal, Forte Sweden, Vinnova Sweden, TÜBITAK Turkey
Resistance at management level	RIF Cyprus, ETAG Estonia, Forte Sweden, Turkey TÜBITAK
Uncertain about terminology	ETAG Estonia, RCL Lithuania, NCRD Poland, FCT Portugal, UEFISCDI Romania, Forte Sweden, Vinnova Sweden, TÜBITAK Turkey
None	NCN Poland
Other	FWO, Belgium Flanders

FWO (Belgium-Flanders) had a comment under “other” where they identified: *“lack of a real, research-based understanding of the (combined) effect of intersectionality and evidence-based measures for dealing with it”*. UEFISCDI Romania and ETAG Estonia mentioned most obstacles. Both RFOs have gender equality policies without additional equality dimensions. In the group of countries with multidimensional equality policies, Lithuania, Turkey, and Cyprus mentioned most obstacles.

Table 13 Number of obstacles identified by RFOs

RFOs with gender equality policies without additional dimensions	Obstacles	RFOs with multidimensional equality policies	Obstacles
Belgium- FWB	0	Belgium-Flanders(FWO)	1
DFF Denmark	1	Cyprus	6
IRC Ireland	4	Czech Republic	4
Romania	9	Italy	3
Estonia	10	Lithuania	8
		Malta	4
		Norway	4
		Poland (NCRD)	6
		Poland (NCN)	1
		Portugal	3
		Spain	3

		Sweden Forte	4
		Sweden Vinnova	4
		Turkey	7

The obstacles mentioned in this benchmark can be used positively to develop the work with a more inclusive and intersectional approach over time. It should be supported and facilitated by national level policy. A unified understanding of concepts is needed. An underlying principle in policy development in general, but particularly in the HE and R&I sector, is that change should be data, research and evidence driven.

Needs identified to lift the intersection of gender with other dimensions.

After looking at obstacles – we now present the responses to an open question to RFO experts on what needs to be done to lift the intersection of gender with other dimensions to the RFOs policy agenda.²⁸ The responses are organized into categories and listed below.

Table 14 Needs identified by RFOs

Type of measure	Suggestions
EC guidelines/	EC initiatives to be 'imposed'
Government guidelines	Intersectional perspectives need to be emphasized in national policies. Instructions from (The) Ministry of Science and Innovation on the relevant axes of discrimination to be considered and the ways of collecting disaggregated data.
Data collection + feedback from underrepresented groups	Minority demographics. A system for feedback on their obstacles to access, experiences.
	Awareness raising with statistics. Targeted initiatives towards underrepresented groups in the innovation system.
	More data on the positive effects of GE in organisations.
Developing knowledge (RFO-centred)	Knowledge on intersectional analysis. Diversity in terms of people (teams), ideas, innovative solutions.
	Knowledge on intersectionality and gender+ approaches, understanding how to work with intersectionality within RFO.
	Further promoting knowledge in other drivers of broad social inequality and non-inclusion. Such as poverty, lack of educational, social, cultural, social assistance infrastructures, the gap between urban centre and peripheries, wider access to education and policies to counteract dropouts across all ISCED levels. Promoting more inter, multi, transdisciplinary studies; involving other stakeholders (Citizen Science), promoting science for policy making. Basic intersectionality knowledge and capabilities to apply practically.
	More knowledge on the benefits of an inclusive culture. How to avoid becoming a target of anti-gender campaigns if you have a more intersectional approach.

²⁸ 4.6 What initiatives and knowledge are needed to lift the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the agenda in your RFO?

	More in-depth and concrete knowledge on what it means, on what the combined effects of different types of inequalities are to people facing them. it is often difficult to really understand the issues in daily professional (or private for that matter) life.
	We need more knowledge on the topic.
	More knowledge on what are the problems, trends and what actions can be taken. It would be good to see best practices from other similar institutions.
Training courses	Study visits, trainings, and meeting to share experiences between agencies would help.
	More awareness, training, and resources.
	Trainings about inclusive language and non-discrimination behaviours.
	Training for more knowledge in the whole organisation for a better understanding of the concept intersectionality and how it can be implemented.
Best practices	Adapting policies towards applicants/beneficiaries.
	A set of evidence-based guidance, measures, good practices etc. to mitigate the intersectional effects of inequalities would be extremely helpful. In summary: the intention to work on intersectionality is definitely there, but it is hard to know what can be done (and what works!) in practice.
	Knowledge on intersectionality and examples from other European agencies would be useful.
	Examples of measures of other RFOs that work with an intersectional perspective in relation to beneficiaries should be summarized (preferably measures that have already been tested).

The way forward – how can these responses be used in future work with intersectionality?

The input regarding obstacles in developing a policy including an intersectional approach in RFOs points to a lack of unified understanding of concepts, lack of data and lack of human resources.

When we look at the open answers on needs identified to lift the intersection of gender with other dimensions, the answers indicate the need for several types of measures. The development of data collection, knowledge adapted to RFOs, sharing good practices and training is given relatively much attention, indicating that this is an area where there is still some uncertainty. Relatively few mention policy guidelines from Governments and the EU.

If we compare these responses to those of the national authorities, the most frequent measures mentioned were mutual learning initiatives, commissioned research and financial incentives or support.

To summarise, when authorities and RFOs identify what is needed to identify the intersection of gender with other dimensions, common elements seem to be developing knowledge/data and making sure there are both human resources and funding available.

At the same time, an intersectional approach at policy level and in research funding organisations seems to require adapting the use of concepts to the relevant institution, gathering knowledge in the given field and mutual learning.

At this point, mutual learning depends on some countries being in the forefront with developing good practices. However, most countries are still evolving their approaches to multidimensional equality work, and few have sufficient research and data collection for intersectional analysis at national level. Few research councils have well established intersectional practices or measures to share.

The findings on obstacles/needs may help in finding a way forward, even if this benchmark survey has not found comprehensive and optimal examples of policies and practices encompassing authorities and RFOs. The first step may be cooperation to promote a unified understanding of concepts when analysing gender in relation to other dimensions in R&I. A second step may be collaboration regarding research and data collection to establish an evidence base for further action. A third step would be developing measures adapted to challenges identified via data collection and research findings.

5.3. Intersectionality as a cross-cutting issue in the other WPs

Questions about intersectional perspectives are mentioned in several work packages (WPs) and tasks in the benchmark. Results of these findings will be presented when different work packages complete their reports in GENDERACTIONplus. However, it is possible to give a brief overview of the responses to these questions here. Below are extracts of texts provided by each task or WP that had included questions about intersectionality.

In summary, questions on intersectionality were included in the benchmarks for the work packages and tasks on inclusive research careers (task 2.2 in WP2), gender-based violence (WP3), the gender dimension in R&I (WP4) and advancing institutional change through GEPs (WP 6). The topic of intersectionality is not dealt with in depth among respondents within most of the mentioned work packages, though it is given some level of attention in the analysis of GBV. It seems apt to categorise integrating intersectional perspectives as an emerging challenge.

Inclusive research careers (WP2, task 2.2)

Findings in responses regarding *inclusive research careers* indicate that this subject is not approached with an intersectional approach in policies of almost all countries. There are discussions on whether national authorities should address careers centrally from their level, namely where tenured-track paths are concerned. Having an intersectional approach is still too recent and not established in the policy narrative, and when present in policies, broad or specific to HE and R&I (as a frequent term, or an explicit approach) – it does not yet translate in a tangible way on inclusive research careers.

In benchmark findings among RFOs regarding inclusive research careers, it seems that RFOs are developing multiple initiatives, but not really focusing on intersections between several grounds of inequality, which effectively account for the interactive impacts among them. Intersectionality is approached mostly in an implicit way, as in the case of TACR (CZ), and is also addressed as a principle, as in the case of FCT (PT).

Gender-based violence and sexual harassment (WP3)

In the research review around half of the articles discuss individual experiences and prevalence of GBV in HE from an intersectional perspective as a way of building more inclusive knowledge. The other half focus on intersectionality as a tool for change. The institutional and structural levels of HE are analysed through an intersectional lens in different ways.

In the policy analysis an intersectional approach is missing throughout the analysed policy documents, with the single exception of Ireland where especially the national framework policy takes important steps towards making visible and using an intersectional lens in its aims and strategies.

Five out of 20 RFOs responding to the GENDERACTIONplus survey have developed policies on GBV since 1 May 2021. Two of these RFOs have indicated an intersectional perspective is included (Irish Research Council, Research Council of Lithuania). This is a somewhat promising result, as the recent

UniSAFE report mapping policy development among RFOs on GBV up until 2020 concluded by stating no RFO in ERA had a policy in place combatting GBV.

In the overall ERA framework on GBV, intersectionality is a cross-cutting priority in recent policy development, but there are still several aspects to develop further. Especially, an intersectional understanding of multiple oppressive forms of discrimination is still missing. Policy development moving beyond a simplistic version of discrimination and an additive model is suggested.

The gender dimension in R&I (WP4)

As for the benchmark analysis on gender dimension in R&I, the survey included a question on intersectionality for those national authorities and RFOs that have specific policies in place to promote sex/gender analysis in R&I content. Only six RFOs (out of 12) have answered "yes" to the question of whether they include an intersectional perspective in their policies to promote the gender dimension in R&I content. The most common equality dimensions include age, disability, and sexual orientation, along with antidiscrimination directives that inform this intersectional approach. However, intersectionality is not dealt with in great depth in gender equality plans of research funders in general, and the theme is described as an emerging challenge (see GENDERACTIONplus Deliverable 4.1).

Advancing institutional change through GEPS (WP6)

Among the countries with a GEP requirement in the HE and R&I sector, Croatia, Greece, Ireland, and Norway include the intersection of different grounds of discrimination, in addition to gender. Ethnicity is most frequent, marked by four countries, followed by age and gender identity (marked by three countries, except Ireland). In Greece, the GEP requirement covers the widest array of intersectional factors. The question of intersectionality is mentioned in a more broadly conceived policy, which recognizes the need to include both gender identity and sexual orientation in measures to combat discrimination, encouraging the holistic treatment of inequalities that run along axes such as gender, identity, and sexuality. Norway also stands out positively – only socio-economic background is not included, but another potential factor of unequal treatment, namely care responsibilities, is mentioned. In Ireland ethnicity is a part of the Athena SWAN charter framework – since the charter has been expanded higher education institutions shall submit intersectional analyses with consideration of ethnicity.

6. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this report we have identified which countries in our sample have inclusive national legislation and policies in place. All responding countries have a national/regional anti-discrimination and/or equal opportunity law and most of these countries have separate laws on gender equality or multidimensional law for the higher education and research and innovation (HE and R&I) sector.

Most countries also have national/regional policies on anti-discrimination and equal opportunity, but fewer have national policies on gender equality for the research sector. Only four of the countries with policies on gender equality also include other equality dimensions in their policies for the HE and RI sector. However, if we include countries with broadly based multidimensional policies for the sector, a majority in the sample of countries have policies that include gender and other equality dimensions for the HE and R&I sector.

Also, for the sample of RFOs, all organisations had a gender equality policy and a majority of these had policies that included equality dimensions in addition to gender. Unlike national authorities, RFOs

lacked broadly based multidimensional policies. An interesting finding was that Belgium-FWB and Ireland, which had specific gender equality policies for HE and R&I including additional dimensions, did not have this in their RFOs policies on gender equality.

Both national authorities and RFOs indicate that they include many equality dimensions in their legislation and policies. When analysing the attached documents (laws and policies), however, these dimensions are not clearly articulated or discussed at any length. Legislation mainly treats equality dimensions separately. However, when so many countries include legislation with multiple equality grounds, there is a potential for national and RFO policies to reflect this and to adopt and encourage an intersectional approach.

Many of the countries and RFOs in the sample identify in the survey that multiple dimensions are included in their laws and policies and many also use terminology that signifies this such as diversity, inclusion, intersectionality. In the analysis of national and RFO policies, however, we only find a few examples of an intersectional approach and very few examples of how the inclusion of several equality dimensions and the use of inclusive terminology is translated into practice in terms of initiatives and measures. In most policies, the need to address several equality dimensions is mentioned, but this manifests as a general statement rather than as an activity with practical implications. In theoretical terms, when several equality dimensions are addressed, it is done either as an add on to gender (a gender+-approach) (European Commission 2022) or as in an additive way treating each equality dimension separately (Advisory Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2020, UniSAFE 2021b). Furthermore, policy documents must pinpoint central challenges so as to suggest guidelines or measures to remedy them. To be more specific, policies need to say more about different groups' relative disadvantage and privilege, taking into account cumulative disadvantage in the intersection of categories. Research on the lived experiences of people on the intersection of different identity categories indicates that some groups (e.g., women with disabilities, ethnic minority women) may be extra vulnerable, but not visible in policy.²⁹ Policy should also address the need for intersectional perspectives in research content.

Although there is a lack of an intersectional approach in laws and policies and very little is translated into practice, the inclusion of more equality dimensions than gender and a use of terminology that also signals a shift in focus is a promising starting point for making laws and policies for MS and AC more inclusive and intersectional in the future.

The identification of obstacles and needs is important for this work to move forward. The responses from national authorities and RFOs were almost identical in identifying which obstacles are most pertinent where the lack of a unified understanding of concepts, disaggregated data and human resources were most dominant. Also, the obstacle "uncertain(ty) about terminology" was mentioned by many. This obstacle can be linked to the lack of a unified understanding of concepts and correlates well with the findings in the GENDERACTIONplus internal needs assessment report 2022 (WP7) that identified knowledge about intersectionality and gender+ approaches as the highest need for the Consortium members. The level of interest identified in the needs assessment report and the need for mutual learning initiatives identified by most respondents in this report, can be viewed as a positive development. It indicates that there is an interest and willingness to move forward in building competence and capacity to lift the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the policy agenda.

²⁹ See for example Rollock (2019) and Gabriel & Tate (2017) on experiences of women of colour or Rummery (2020) on corresponding experiences of women with disabilities in academic positions.

In the sample there were great contextual differences both at national authority and RFO level. While in some countries there is a struggle to put gender equality on the agenda, other countries have had several equality dimensions in their legislation and policies for years. The greatest variation in our sample is between the Nordic countries and Ireland, and some Central European countries.

The evidence from this benchmarking exercise corroborates the findings in the informal mapping carried out by the ERAC SWG GRI Intersectionality Taskforce and recent studies mentioned in chapter 2 Policy background. These are reports such as the Approaches to inclusive gender equality in research and innovation (European Commission 2022) and the Pilot assessment activities for the European knowledge and facility on GEPs in research and innovation organizations (European Commission 2023) and SheFigures 2021. In all these documents it was stated that working with multiple equality dimensions or having legislation or policies with an intersectional approach is an emerging field of work that can only be identified in a few European countries. In the laws/policies that were referenced by respondents in our study, there were some patterns that began to emerge. Most of these laws/policies contained broad statements on equal rights and multiple grounds of discrimination protected under law, yet few demonstrated a truly intersectional approach. Indeed, where additional grounds of discrimination were being addressed, this tended to fall under broad equality legislation, used as statements in policies and take an additive approach to dealing with equality beyond gender equality. As was also the conclusion in the studies referred to above, there were few examples of a move from a general approach to inclusion and intersectionality towards translating this into concrete policy objectives and actions. Barriers such as a unified understanding of concepts and terminology and the lack of equality data beyond gender were also similar to previous findings.

Another issue that is often discussed in connection to including more equality dimensions in law and policies, is whether measures and actions identified mostly build on prior gender equality activity (a gender +-perspective). In our material, we see that other dimensions are often an add on to gender and that there is no discussion about whether this makes these equality dimensions a second priority to gender in how they are included and discussed in law and policy. The countries where prior studies have identified good practices are coinciding with countries in our sample who have managed to go beyond statements identifying good measures and initiatives. Countries such as Austria, France, Germany, Ireland, and Norway are often mentioned. In our sample, we found examples from Ireland and Norway to be most advanced although it was only in documents from Ireland where we could identify fragments of a truly intersectional approach. The Irish example is particularly interesting, as it shows how an intersectional approach to policy design (at local and national level) can be taken, even when there is a lack of truly intersectional data. This should act as an encouragement to MS and AC to move beyond the argument that an intersectional approach can only be taken where intersecting data is collected across multiple equality dimensions.

Although the result from this benchmark confirms that the work on inclusion and intersectionality in HE and R&I sector in MS and AC in the ERA is at an early stage, there are several factors that point to a promising shift and a positive development. European research and innovation policy is increasingly recognizing diversity, inclusion, and intersectionality as decisive factors for academic career progression. This is manifested in instrumental policy documents and identified priorities, research and the development of tools commissioned by the EU Commission and initiatives supported by MS and AC. Also, other important bodies in the HE and R&I sector such as EUA, LERU and the Guild, are pushing for a shift to a more inclusive academy. In this report it was identified that many countries in the sample have legislation and policies at both national and RFO level that includes several equality dimensions in addition to gender. Through the obstacles and needs identified by the respondents, we found an interest in moving forward from addressing inclusion and intersectionality in documents in an additive manner as statements to translating policy and legislation into initiatives and measures with an intersectional approach. It will take time, competence building and support for this development to

take place, but with a continuous focus from the EU and national governments in strategies and policies we should be able to see a shift to a more inclusive and intersectional focus in European HE and R&I sector in the future.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The writing of this report has been a long process and we have many to thank. We would like to thank all partners in the GENDERACTIONplus project for co-creating the benchmark survey and for your inputs and advice in workshops on benchmark analysis. Your experience and knowledge have been of great value to the report and will be important for putting the work on diversity, inclusion, and intersectionality higher on the national and European policy agenda. We also would like to thank our leader, Ragnhild Hennum and reference group in the Committee for Gender Balance and Diversity in Research (KIF), Julia Orupabo, Yan Zhao and Ronald Mayora Synnes for good discussions and input. A big thank you to Kaja Kathrine Wendt at Statistics Norway for invaluable help in the processing of data and presentation of results. Thank you to our partners in WP2, Maria João Sequeira and Maria do Rosário Costa for important and encouraging input in the analysis and writing process and to Eva Sophia Myers for support overall. Many thanks to Lydia González Orta for a thorough and important quality check of a draft version of this report. Thank you, Karina Lystad, for your invaluable assistance and support in keeping the KIF-secretariat running during the writing process. Lastly, a big thank you to Marcela Linková for good input and advice along the way and for the work you do as a leader and coordinator for GENDERACTIONplus lifting equality, inclusion, and intersectionality high on the agenda in European policy work for higher education, research, and innovation.

8. REFERENCES

Advisory Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men (2020). Opinion on Intersectionality in Gender Equality, Laws, Policies and Practices [opinion_intersectionality_2020_en_0.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

Christoffersen, A. (2021): The politics of intersectional practice: Competing concepts of intersectionality, *Policy and Politics*, 49(4): 573–593.
<https://doi.org/10.1332/030557321X16194316141034>

Collins, P.H., da Silva, E.C.G., Ergun, E. *et al.* (2021): Intersectionality as Critical Social Theory. *Contemp Polit Theory*, 20: 690–725. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41296-021-00490-0>

Crenshaw, K. (1989): Demarginalizing the intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory and Antiracist Politics. University of Chicago Legal Forum.

ERAC Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation (SWG GRI), Position paper on the future gender equality priority in the ERA 2020-2030 (ERAC 1204/20), [pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

EUA (2019): Diversity, Equity and Inclusion in European Higher Education Institutions, Results from the INVITED project, [Publications \(eua.eu\)](#)

European Commission (2017): Legal Framework and practice in the EU member states, Analysis and comparative review of equality data collection practices in the European Union, DOI:10.2838/6934 [analysis and comparative review of equality data collection-DS0217200ENN.pdf](#)

European Commission (2018): Guidelines on improving the collection and use of equality data, High Level Group on Non-discrimination, Equality and Diversity. Doi:10.2838/9725 [en-guidelines-improving-collection-and-use-of-equality-data.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

European Commission (2020): Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, The Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the regions A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, COM/2020/152 final. [EUR-Lex - 52020DC0152 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](#)

European Commission (2020): EU Anti-racism Action Plan 2020-2025. (COM(2020) 565 final) [a union of equality eu action plan against racism 2020 -2025 en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

European Commission, 2020, EU Roma Strategic Framework for Equality, Inclusion and Participation 2020-2030 (COM (2020) 620 final) [eu roma strategic framework for equality inclusion and participation for 2020 - 2030 0.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

European Commission (2020): Speech by Commissioner Dalli: Union of Equality: LGBTQI Equality Strategy 2020-2025. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/speech_20_2126

European Commission, (2020): Communication from the Commission “A new ERA for Research and Innovation” (COM/2020/628 final, [EUR-Lex - 52020DC0628 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](#))

European Commission (2020): The Council Conclusions on the New European Research Area (13567/20, [pdf \(europa.eu\)](#))

European Commission (2021): Guidance note on the collection and use of equality data based on racial or ethnic origin. doi:10.2838/06180 [Guidance Note on the collection and use of equality data based on racial or ethnic origin \(europa.eu\)](#)

European Commission (2021): Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, She figures 2021 : policy briefs, Publications Office, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/078011>

European Commission (2021): Union of equality: Strategy for the rights of persons with disabilities 2021-2030. (COM (2021) 101 final) [union of equality-KE0221257ENN.pdf](#)

European Commission (2022): Approaches to inclusive gender equality in research and innovation (R&I) DOI:10.2777/004694 [approaches to inclusive gender equality in research-KI0122348ENN \(3\).pdf](#)

European Commission (2023): Pilot assessment activities for the European knowledge and facility on GEPs in research and innovation organisations. – due to be published

European Institute for Gender Equality: [intersectionality | European Institute for Gender Equality \(europa.eu\)](#)

European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (2018): Handbook on European non-discrimination law – 2018 edition, <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2018/handbook-european-non-discrimination-law-2018-edition>

Farkas, L. (2017): Analysis and comparative review of equality and data collection practices in the European Union. Data collection in the field of ethnicity, Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers. <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/just/document>.

Fredman, Sandra (2016): Opinion on Intersectionality in Gender Equality Laws, Policies and Practices, [Intersectional discrimination in EU gender equality and non-discrimination law - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#)

Gabriel, D. & Tate, S.A (2017): Inside the Ivory Tower Narratives of women of colour surviving and thriving in British Academia. Trentham Books.

GENDERACTION briefing paper n1, 2018, [GENDERACTION_PolicyBriefs_1-10.pdf](#)

The Guild, Opening a dialogue on gender equality, diversity and inclusion at European universities (2022). [the-guild_gender-diversity-definitions_8march2022.pdf](#)

League of European Research Universities (LERU) Equality, diversity and inclusion at universities: the power of a systemic approach (LERU position paper 2019) [Equality, diversity and inclusion at universities: the power of a systemic approach | LERU](#)

Ljubljana Declaration (2021): Gender Equality in Research and Innovation. https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MIZS/Dokumenti/PSEU/Ljubljana-Declaration-on-Gender-Equality-in-Research-and-Innovation-_endorsed_final.pdf

Lombardo, Emanuela & Mieke Verloo (2009): Institutionalizing Intersectionality in the European Union?, *International Feminist Journal of Politics*, 11:4, 478-495, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616740903237442>

Nash, J. C. (2008): Re-thinking intersectionality, *Feminist Review*, 89: 1–15. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40663957>

Nichols, Sue and Garth Stahl (2019): Intersectionality in higher education research: a systematic literature review, *Higher Education Research & Development*, DOI: [10.1080/07294360.2019.1638348](https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2019.1638348)

Norlen, H., Papadimitriou, E. and Dijkstra, L. (2019): The regional gender equality monitor, EUR 29679 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/regional-gender-equality-monitor>

Palmén, Rachel (2021, October): ACT on intersectionality. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5602859>

Rollock, Nicola (2019): Staying power: the career experiences and strategies of UK Black female Professors. Project Report. UCU, London.

Rummery, K. (2020): From the personal to the political: Ableism, activism and academia. In N. Brown & J. Leigh (Eds.), *Ableism in Academia: Theorising experiences of disabilities and chronic illnesses in higher education* (pp. 182–201). UCL Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv13xprj.17>

Täuber, Susanne (2022): Women Academics' Intersectional Experiences of Policy Ineffectiveness in the European Context. *Front. Psychol.* 13:810569. DOI: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.810569

UniSAFE (2021b): UniSAFE D3.2 Report on the European Policy Baseline. <https://zenodo.org/record/5780037#.YmuOXt-xU2y>

Woods, D. R., Benschop, Y., & van den Brink, M. (2022): What is intersectional equality? A definition and goal of equality for organizations. *Gender, Work & Organization*, 29(1), 92–109 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gwao.12760>

9. ANNEXES

Appendix A – Benchmark survey questions for national authorities

GENDERACTIONplus: BENCHMARKING OF NATIONAL/REGIONAL POLICIES

Scope and objective: This is a benchmarking exercise of **national (and regional as relevant) policies on gender equality in research, higher education and innovation** (NP on GE in RHEI) and focuses on the five thematic areas of GENDERACTIONplus (intersectionality and inclusiveness; gender-based violence; gender dimension in research, innovation and teaching; monitoring and evaluation in the ERA; institutional change through gender equality plans). **The objective is to establish what is in place in each country and what are emerging good practices we can learn from.**

Background: In 2021, gender equality in higher education, research and innovation has been reaffirmed as a priority for the new European Research Area (ERA).¹ By end of June 2022, Member States have indicated their interest in addressing ERA Action 5 (Gender equality and inclusiveness). New policy areas identified include intersectionality and inclusiveness and gender-based violence in academia. Further policy attention is required in the areas of the gender dimension in teaching, research and innovation; monitoring and evaluation of ERA policies and advancing institutional change through Gender Equality Plans, including monitoring and evaluation of the impact of GEPs on gender equality.

This benchmark is to set ground for current policies and developments at the national and regional level as relevant. As such, it will be an important contribution to ERA Policy Action 5 as the project is expected to provide policy input and advice on ERA Policy Action 5.

We kindly request all partners to provide as full answers as possible, including the links to potential policy documents and translations of the relevant text of the policy. Not answering a question or not providing information about policies when they are in place should be a last resort. Thank you!

With this benchmark, information is pursued that is not obtainable in other ways and hence the contribution of the project partners is vital.

Timeframe: 2017 – present time unless specified otherwise; the focus is on policies that are in force now and recent evolution

Who should complete: One answer per country is requested. Project partners (both beneficiaries and Associated Partners) are responsible for coordinating input to the benchmark with other relevant national bodies (as the case may be). Given the cooperation may be required between different national authorities or responsible persons in completing the benchmark survey, the questionnaire can be downloaded and shared as a .doc file. **The deadline for providing your input in the LimeSurvey is 6 November 2022.**

Main definitions

- **Law** is a set of rules that are created and enforceable by social or governmental institutions to regulate behaviour, adopted through a defined legislative process.
- **Policy** is a deliberate system of guidelines to guide decisions and achieve outcomes. It is a statement of intent and is implemented as a procedure or protocol. Policies are generally

adopted by a governance body within an organization. For the purpose of this benchmark, policies are defined as adopted by national or regional governments in the form of official regulations, and procedures officially adopted by the governing body in the form of a document.

- **Policy measure** is an action taken by the national / regional authority that may be one-off, not embedded in a policy document and agreed.

A [glossary](#) is attached providing definitions of key concepts.

Notes:

- **in the case of requests for document translations to English, if there is/are no official document(s), machine translation(s) is/are sufficient;**
- **otherwise, an official institutional position is sought unless requested explicitly otherwise.**

¹ Communication from the Commission A new ERA for Research and Innovation ([COM/2020/628 final](#)); Council Conclusions on the New European Research Area of 1 December 2020 ([13567/20](#)); Council Conclusions on the future governance of the European Research Area ([14308/21](#)); The Ljubljana Declaration on Gender Equality in Research and Innovation (available [here](#)); [EU Pact for Research and Innovation](#).

There are 158 questions in this survey.

1. Background information

1.1 Partner institution *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- BUNDESMINISTERIUM FUER BILDUNG, WISSENSCHAFT UND FORSCHUNG
- Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science + Independent Research Fund Denmark, DFF
- Departement Economy, Science and Innovation
- Deutsches Zentrum für Luft
- FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGÍA, F.S.P., FECYT
- GOETEBORGS UNIVERSITET
- Higher Education Authority
- Institute for Advanced Studies
- Institute of Sociology of the Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic
- JOANNEUM RESEARCH FORSCHUNGSGESELLSCHAFT MBH
- Kunnskapsdepartementet
- Malta Council for Science and Technology (MCST)
- Maynooth University
- MINISTRY OF EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND SPORT (MIZS)
- Ministry of Education, Science and Sport of the Republic of Lithuania
- Ministry of Innovation, Science & Technology (MOST)

- Ministry of Science and Education (MZO)
- Ministry of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation
- National Commission for the Promotion of Equality
- National Documentation Centre
- National Information Processing Institute
- SYDDANSK UNIVERSITET
- Univerzita Mateja Bela
- VETENSKAP & ALLMANHET, VA
- Vilnius University Šiauliai Academy

1.2 Country *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- AT
- BE-Flanders
- BE-FWB
- CZ
- DE
- DK
- EL
- ES
- HR
- IE
- IL
- LT
- MT
- NO
- PL
- SE
- SI
- SK

1.3 Contact person for the benchmarking exercise (the person to be potentially contacted in the event supplementary information is needed).

*

Please write your answer here:

1.4 Email *

Please write your answer here:

1.5 Main responsible national authority responding to the benchmark: *

Please write your answer here:

1.6 Other national authorities contributing to the benchmark completion *

Please write your answer here:

1.7 Method of benchmark completion (please comment on the process of data and information gathering; especially for partners appointed by national authorities, comment on whether the answers reflect your expert assessment or whether they reflect the official position of the national authorities you have been appointed to represent in the project).

*

Please write your answer here:

2. National/regional anti-discrimination and/or equality laws and policies

This section serves to establish the existence of the main national laws and policies on gender equality / anti-discrimination / equal opportunities.

2.1 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination and/or equal opportunity laws? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a name and link to the main national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity law if relevant (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

For example, in the Czech Republic, this would be the [Antidiscrimination Act](#); this question is NOT asking about the law on higher education.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '8 [B21]' (2.1 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination and/or equal opportunity laws?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s) and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '8 [B21]' (2.1 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination and/or equal opportunity laws?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

2.2 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a name and link to the national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

For example, in the Czech Republic, this would be the [Gender Equality Strategy for 2021 – 2030](#); this question is NOT about the higher education policy or research, development and innovation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '11 [B22]' (2.2 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s) and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '11 [B22]' (2.2 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

3. New European Research Area (ERA)

Previous ERA National Action Plans (NAPs) have been particularly successful when based on a broad commitment. This section therefore seeks to establish the process through which the national authorities have determined the actions to sign up for in the new ERA.

3.1 Has the process of identifying the new ERA Actions to sign up for been participatory (e.g., organised events such as round tables or consultations with relevant stakeholders)?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify who has been involved in the process including the departments/units responsible for gender equality/diversity/equal opportunities.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '14 [C31]' (3.1 Has the process of identifying the new ERA Actions to sign up for been participatory (e.g., organised events such as round tables or consultations with relevant stakeholders)?)

Please write your answer here:

3.2 Do the ERA Action 5 topics included in the national response build on existing policy priorities and actions?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, which ones (such as national policy, the previous ERA NAPs): *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '16 [C32]' (3.2 Do the ERA Action 5 topics included in the national response build on existing policy priorities and actions?)

Please write your answer here:

4. Overall assessment of gender equality laws and policies in higher education and research and

This section serves to assess the existence of laws and policies specifically on gender equality in higher education and research and innovation and establish whether it is a priority for the national / regional authorities, who is responsible and what the most recent developments are.

As an example, the Czech Republic does not have a specific law or policy on gender equality in higher education and/or research so will answer "No" to 4.1 and 4.2. There is a [National RDI Policy Czech Republic 2021+](#) which addresses equality and work-life balance and there is [Gender Equality Strategy 2021-2030](#) which has a section dedicated to Knowledge (education and research). Hence, the answer will be "Yes" to 4.2.2 and these two documents would be provided.

4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

4.1.1 If yes, which bodies/authorities are responsible for implementing the law?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please write your answer here:

4.1.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived law on higher education, law on research and innovation or equality law?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify. Please provide a name and link (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '20 [D412]' (4.1.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived law on higher education, law on research and innovation or equality law?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '20 [D412]' (4.1.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived law on higher education, law on research and innovation or equality law?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

4.2.1 If yes, which institution/s are responsible for implementing the policy?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please write your answer here:

4.2.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived policy on higher education, policy on research and innovation or their combination or equality policy?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages and if not in English, provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '25 [D422]' (4.2.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived policy on higher education, policy on research and innovation or their combination or equality policy?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document, specify the relevant passages and if not in English, provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '25 [D422]' (4.2.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived policy on higher education, policy on research and innovation or their combination or equality policy?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

4.3 What are the most important policy developments at the national / regional level (as relevant) on gender equality in RHEI in the last two years (e.g., adoption of whole new policy, adoption of a policy framework on fighting gender-based violence in higher education, adoption of a GEP requirement for all HEIs in the country etc.)?

*

Please write your answer here:

4.4 What have been the main facilitating factors for these developments?

*

Please write your answer here:

4.5a Please provide a name and link to the new developments at the national / regional level in question 4.3. Please provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Please write your answer here:

4.5b If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s) (please provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation).

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

4.6 What have been the main hindering factors for advancing gender equality policy in RHEI?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Resistance at institutional level
- Lack of economic resources
- Lack of human resources
- Lack of interest
- Not regarded as relevant
- Lack of research-based knowledge and data
- Other:

4.7 Have any policies / actions / activities been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

4.7.1 If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '33 [D47]' (4.7 Have any policies / actions / activities been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?)

Please write your answer here:

4.8 Have any policies / actions / activities been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

4.8.1 If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '35 [D48]' (4.8 Have any policies / actions / activities been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?)

Please write your answer here:

4.9 Specifically, to what extent has the [Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion](#) had an effect on gender equality in research & innovation in your country?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- To no extent
- To little extent
- To some extent
- To a large extent
- To a very large extent

4.9.1 What concrete effect the GEP requirement has had? *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- New GEPs have been approved in R&I institutions
- Workshops and training have been organised in the R&I field on GEPs at the national level
- An increase in requests/questions received by NCPs as a result of the eligibility criterion
- The EC recommended thematic areas have opened new lines of action in R&I institutions
- New tools and material developed on developing and implementing GEPs in R&I
- Increased national funding for GEP development
- Other:

4.9.2 Additional comment (please provide any other relevant information about the effect of the GEP requirement or discussions surrounding it that will help to better understand and contextualise the information provided in the survey). Please add NA if not applicable.

*

Please write your answer here:

5. Intersectionality

The Commission has stated a wish to broaden gender equality policies in research and innovation to intersections with other potential grounds for discrimination such as ethnicity, disability and sexual orientation. This section of the survey serves to assess to what extent this is addressed in EU Member States and Associated Countries.

5.1 Does the national/regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation address one or more of the following dimensions?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

Please provide a link to this law and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.2 Is this a recent development (last 3-5 years)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes

- No

5.3 If you do not have a national/regional law on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in a more broadly conceived national/regional law for higher education, research and innovation?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '44 [E53]' (5.3 If you do not have a national/regional law on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in a more broadly conceived national/regional law for higher education, research and innovation?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document, specify the relevant passages, and if not in English, provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '44 [E53]' (5.3 If you do not have a national/regional law on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in a more broadly conceived national/regional law for higher education, research and innovation?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.4 If you have a national/regional policy on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, does this policy also address one or more of the following dimensions?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- None
- Other:

5.5 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your policy and initiatives, what are the terms most frequently used? Please tick all that apply:

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Non-discrimination
- Intersectionality
- Representation
- Gender+ equality
- Diversity
- Inclusiveness/inclusion
- Inclusive equality
- Equity/equality
- Other:

Please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please write your answer here:

Or please please upload the document, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.6 If you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is this a recent development (last 3-5 years)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide examples. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.7.1 Does this policy also address one or more of the following dimensions. Please tick all that apply:

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

5.7.2 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your policy, what are the terms most frequently used? Please tick all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Non-discrimination
- Intersectionality

- Representation
- Gender+ equality
- Diversity
- Inclusiveness/inclusion
- Inclusive equality
- Equity/equality
- None of the above
- Other:

Please provide a link, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.7.3 Is the inclusion of the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.) a recent development (last 3-5 years)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.8 Has your ministry or any other relevant national/regional authority faced any of the following obstacles in developing a policy including an intersectional approach? Please tick all that apply.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Uncertainty about the terminology to be used
- Lack of a unified understanding of the underlying concepts
- Gender equality as a policy topic is a struggle without other inequality grounds
- Resistance at higher education/research institutions
- Legal regulations restricting data collection (e.g., personal data protection)
- Lack of human resources
- Lack of economic resources
- Lack of interest / not regarded to be relevant
- Lack of disaggregated data on ethnic and other minorities
- Lack of research-based knowledge on gender and diversity in research in your country
- None
- Other:

5.9 Do you have national measures to support the implementation of inclusive/ intersectional policies in research?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.9.1 If yes, please tick all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '61 [E59]' (5.9 Do you have national measures to support the implementation of inclusive/ intersectional policies in research?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Reporting to national authorities on gender balance indicators

- Reporting to national authorities on indicators on other grounds of inequality (ethnicity, socio-economic status, age, disability etc.)
- National conferences
- Financial incentives (e.g., support to institutions for recruiting women in STEMM)
- Advisory centres for gender equality
- National committees appointed by ministries or other national bodies
- National awareness-raising campaigns
- Other:

5.10 What initiatives and knowledge are needed to lift the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the policy agenda at your ministry and on the policy agenda in the European Research Area? Please tick all that apply:

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Mutual learning initiatives
- Clear guidelines from the EC
- Advanced legal framework at national level
- Financial incentives and support
- Research commissioned on how to address the intersection of gender equality with other potential grounds of discrimination
- I don't know
- Other:

6. Inclusive research careers

The purpose of Section 6 is to map current and emerging strategies and policies on research careers. Through the information collected and analysed - pinpointing patterns, gaps and solutions, and deepening evidence-based knowledge - we will be able to develop strategic policy recommendations in order to promote more inclusive careers across MS and AC, careers conceived through the intersectional perspective. This converges with the challenge of building the new ERA, in line with the [Council Conclusions Deepening the European Research Area: Providing researchers with attractive and sustainable careers and working conditions and making brain circulation a reality](#), [Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe](#) and the [ERA Policy Agenda](#) (especially at the crossroad of Actions 4 and 5).

6.1 Are there national strategies/policies/policy measures in place, specifically focused on research careers in higher education and research and innovation institutions in your country?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '64 [F61]' (6.1 Are there national strategies/policies/policy measures in place, specifically focused on research careers in higher education and research and innovation institutions in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify (provide a link to the document online, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify (provide a link to the document online, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please tick all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

Please, identify the strategies/policies/policy instruments, provide links and quote the exact references to the policies in 6.1 and 6. 2. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.3 Is attention to inclusive research careers in national policies or strategies a recent development (less than 3 years) or an established area of work (more than 3 years)? Please specify.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '75 [F63]' (6.3 Is attention to inclusive research careers in national policies or strategies a recent development (less than 3 years) or an established area of work (more than 3 years)? Please specify.)

Please write your answer here:

6.4 What do the inclusive measures of these strategies/policies/policy initiatives focus on? Tick all that apply:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Gender equality
- Gender bias
- Equal access to employment
- Career progression (including recruiting women to professorship and/ or academic leadership)
- Job Precarity
- Gender pay-gap
- Early careers
- Nonlinear careers
- International mobility
- Intersectoral mobility
- Interdisciplinary mobility
- Portability of social security
- Work-life balance
- Working conditions
- Skills and employability
- Professional visibility /recognition
- Research assessment
- Other:

Please add a short text to explain the context and content of all the previously selected measures in 6.4

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

6.4.1 Has Research Assessment been a topic before the launch of the [Reforming Research Assessment Initiative](#) and under action 3 of the European Research Area Policy Agenda?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '77 [F64]' (6.4 What do the inclusive measures of these strategies/policies/policy initiatives focus on? Tick all that apply:)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

6.4.2 Do any of the criteria for research assessment address gender inequality or other grounds of discrimination (across disciplines, research types, career stages, research roles, peer review, training and mentoring, other...)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '77 [F64]' (6.4 What do the inclusive measures of these strategies/policies/policy initiatives focus on? Tick all that apply:)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '80 [F642]' (6.4.2 Do any of the criteria for research assessment address gender inequality or other grounds of discrimination (across disciplines, research types, career stages, research roles, peer review, training and mentoring, other...)?)

Please write your answer here:

6.5 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your policy, what are the terms most frequently used in your policies and initiatives on inclusive research careers?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Non-discrimination
- Intersectionality
- Representation
- Gender+ equality
- Diversity
- Inclusiveness/inclusion

- Inclusive equality
- Equity/equality
- None of the above
- Other:

Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation). Please comment/explain especially if multiple terms are used (non-mandatory)

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please write your answer here:

Or upload the document, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.6 Is there any kind of evaluation process on already adopted / implemented policies / initiatives? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, what are the key factors for the success in implementation? Please specify:

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '85 [F66]' (6.6 Is there any kind of evaluation process on already adopted / implemented policies / initiatives?)

Please write your answer here:

6.7 Is there a difference in the social security coverage in your country between different types of researcher positions (permanent or temporary) and PhD students on fellowships, in the following situations?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

6.7.1 If yes, tick all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '87 [F67]' (6.7 Is there a difference in the social security coverage in your country between different types of researcher positions (permanent or temporary) and PhD students on fellowships, in the following situations?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Illness
- Unemployment
- Work-life Balance
- Maternity and parental leave / support (e.g., length and allowance during the leave, ...) and post maternity /parental leave support while back to work
- Retirement
- Other:

6.7.2 Please explain shortly the differences in coverage in each selected situation: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '87 [F67]' (6.7 Is there a difference in the social security coverage in your country between different types of researcher positions (permanent or temporary) and PhD students on fellowships, in the following situations?)

Please write your answer here:

6.7.3 Please identify in which of the above situations ticked in 6.7, gender discrimination, direct or indirect, is more likely to occur and what are the conditions (different conditions in the coverage by social security, work-life balance in Fellowship Holder Statutes versus General Labour Code, etc.).

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '87 [F67]' (6.7 Is there a difference in the social security coverage in your country between different types of researcher positions (permanent or temporary) and PhD students on fellowships, in the following situations?)

Please write your answer here:

6.8 Are there other debates ongoing at the national level for more inclusive Social Security coverage?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '91 [F68]' (6.8 Are there other debates ongoing at the national level for more inclusive Social Security coverage?)

Please write your answer here:

6.9 Has your ministry or any other relevant national/regional authority faced any of the following obstacles in developing policies/policy initiatives and actions on gender-inclusive research careers?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Uncertainty about the terminology to be used
- Lack of a unified understanding of the underlying concepts
- Prevalent masculine notions about the research profession (total dedication, extreme focus on performance etc.)
- Not yet on the national agenda
- Still under preliminary debate
- Lack of political /societal awareness
- Lack of Gender Equality Structures
- Budgetary constraints
- Lack of gender disaggregated data
- None of the above
- Other:

6.10 What initiatives are needed to raise the issue of inclusive research careers on the national and European agenda? *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Mutual learning initiatives
- Clear guidelines from the European Commission (EC)
- Advanced legal framework at national level
- Financial incentives and support
- Other:

6.11 Based on your experience, what recommendations could you provide at the national level to promote the design and implementation of gender inclusive research careers?

Please write your answer here:

6.12 Please share case studies or good practices that have helped your country in strengthening inclusive research careers.

Please write your answer here:

7. Gender-Based Violence

Instruction: Please read your country reports from the UniSAFE project available on [the Zenodo community](#) (please use the search box at the top of the page to search for your country's national report) and indicate any new developments since 1 May 2021. Please note that the UniSAFE project covers EU-27 and among the Associated Countries Iceland, UK, Serbia, and Turkey.

Gender-Based Violence (GBV) is defined as all forms of gendered violations and abuse, including but not limited to, physical violence, psychological violence, economic and financial violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender harassment, stalking, organisational violence and harassment. GBV can occur in both online and offline contexts, and also includes emerging forms of violence, experienced as violence, violations and abuse not yet necessarily named or recognised as violence.

Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) are defined as any public or private body financing research and innovation.

7.1. Have national policies been adopted to address GBV in RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan). These policies may target applicants for funding and the entire funding process, as well as the internal organisation of the RFO itself.

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '97 [G71]' (7.1. Have national policies been adopted to address GBV in RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan). These policies may target applicants for funding and the entire funding process, as well as the internal organisation of the RFO itself.)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '98 [G611]' (If yes, does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not available online please upload the document and highlight the relevant text. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '98 [G611]' (If yes, does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

If it is planned, please name the policy and any possible details already known.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '97 [G71]' (7.1. Have national policies been adopted to address GBV in RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan). These policies may target applicants for funding and the entire funding process, as well as the internal organisation of the RFO itself.)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '97 [G71]' (7.1. Have national policies been adopted to address GBV in RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan). These policies may target applicants for funding and the entire funding process, as well as the internal organisation of the RFO itself.)

Please write your answer here:

7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- It is planned
- No, and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '103 [G72]' (7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not available online, please upload the document and highlight the relevant text. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '103 [G72]' (7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

If it is planned, please name the policy and any possible details already known.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'It is planned' at question '103 [G72]' (7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No, and it is not planned' at question '103 [G72]' (7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?)

Please write your answer here:

7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '108 [G73]' (7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not available online, please upload the document and highlight the relevant text. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '108 [G73]' (7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

If it is planned, please name the policy and any possible details already known.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '108 [G73]' (7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '108 [G73]' (7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

8. Gender dimension in research, teaching and innovation

This section focuses specifically on national initiatives – and regional where relevant – to promote the integration of the gender dimension in the content of research and innovation projects (i.e., sex/gender analysis in R&I). Note that these questions are not about gender balance in R&I teams. We encourage you to check our [glossary](#) for clarification of the concepts related to this section.

8.1 What kind of actions have been taken by your national authority at national level to promote the integration of the gender dimension into R&I?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Financial incentives/support to promote the gender dimension in research and innovation
- Financial incentives/support to promote the gender dimension in teaching content
- A specific funding programme on gender studies is in place
- Requiring applicants to specify whether they are considering sex and/or gender in their research/ innovation proposal
- Inclusion of gender experts in the research teams is encouraged in the R&I calls
- Training on sex/gender analysis for the research team is considered as an eligible cost in national funding schemes
- Established processes to evaluate the integration of the sex/gender analysis into R&I (i.e., as part of the institution's mandate and through well-established guidelines on the evaluation)
- Positive action measures to favour projects that integrate sex and/or gender (go to the glossary for a definition of positive action measures)
- Guidelines on the gender dimension of R&I for applicants
- Guidelines on the gender dimension of R&I for evaluators
- Training on the gender dimension of R&I for applicants
- Training on the gender dimension of R&I for evaluators
- Experts on gender in R&I are included in the evaluation committees
- Communication campaign to make visible the support to sex/gender analysis
- Dissemination materials on the gender dimension in R&I available (videos, academic papers, leaflets...)
- Actions to promote sex/gender analysis in university-level curricula
- None of the above
- Other:

8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

8.2.1 If no, does your national authority plan to make a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please explain the context of the plans: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '115 [H821]' (8.2.1 If no, does your national authority plan to make a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.3 What kind of strategy or policy has your national authority adopted? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- National law
- Specific strategy, policy and/or measure (e.g., gender equality plan)
- Other:

Please provide the name of your national/regional official policy related to the information requested above, link(s) to supporting documents you consider relevant for the analysis and specify the relevant passages (if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages, and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

8.4 What are the main goals of your strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.5 Does your national/regional strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I include an intersectional approach?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

8.5.1 If yes, tick off for which inequality grounds: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '121 [H85]' (8.5 Does your national/regional strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I include an intersectional approach?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

8.6 Does your national/regional strategy or policy include the innovation and private sectors in the objective of producing non-biased knowledge and solutions for society as a whole?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

8.7 How is the strategy/policy on the gender dimension in R&I implemented? Please provide information on the unit(s) responsible for implementing the policy, the actions taken so far, and the structures developed for its implementation, including technical, human and economic resources.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.8 How is the policy/strategy on the gender dimension in R&I monitored? Please provide information on the actions and structures, if any, established to supervise the concrete actions

developed by this national authority/other agents of the R&I system, the indicators used and their outcomes.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.9 Has the policy/strategy on the gender dimension in R&I been evaluated? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, what impact/outcome has your policy on the gender dimension in R&I made? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '126 [H89]' (8.9 Has the policy/strategy on the gender dimension in R&I been evaluated?)

Please write your answer here:

8.10 Please explain the challenges/obstacles, if any, the national authority/ies has/have faced in implementing this policy/strategy on the gender dimension in R&I:

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.11 If relevant, do regional RFOs in your country require the integration of the gender dimension in R&I projects?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable

8.12 Does your national authority have a policy or strategy aimed at promoting sex/gender analysis in university-level curricula?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '130 [H12]' (8.12 Does your national authority have a policy or strategy aimed at promoting sex/gender analysis in university-level curricula?)

Please write your answer here:

Or upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '130 [H12]' (8.12 Does your national authority have a policy or strategy aimed at promoting sex/gender analysis in university-level curricula?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

8.13 What would your national authority need to advance some of the measures mentioned above or others to promote the gender dimension in the R&I content?

*

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Financial resources
- More awareness on the relevance on sex/gender analysis for R&I
- Exchange experiences on how to consider the gender dimension in R&I from an intersectional perspective
- Capacity-building
- Training materials
- Mandatory policies (e.g., conditional funding)
- I don't know

- Other:

9. GEP monitoring / Evaluating GEP impact

9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

9.2 If yes, is it mandated by:

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- The law
- A policy
- Both
- Other

9.3 To which organisations does the GEP requirement apply? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Public HEIs
- Private HEIs
- Public RPOs
- Private RPOs
- Public administration bodies
- Private R&I sector companies with a certain number of employees
- Other:

9.4 Does the GEP requirement include intersections with other discriminatory grounds?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please tick all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '137 [J94]' (9.4 Does the GEP requirement include intersections with other discriminatory grounds?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Ethnicity,
- Socio-economic background/class
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

9.5 Is the GEP requirement envisioned to contribute to the development of Inclusive Research Careers?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '139 [J95]' (9.5 Is the GEP requirement envisioned to contribute to the development of Inclusive Research Careers?)

Please write your answer here:

9.6 Does the national GEP requirement fulfil the following EU GEP mandatory building blocks?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please tick all that are required:

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '141 [J960]' (9.6 Does the national GEP requirement fulfil the following EU GEP mandatory building blocks?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Publication: a formal document published on the institution's website and signed by the top management
- Dedicated resources: commitment of resources and expertise in gender equality to implement the plan
- Data collection and monitoring: sex/gender disaggregated data on personnel (and students, for the establishments concerned) and annual reporting based on indicators
- Training: awareness raising/training on gender equality and unconscious gender biases for staff and decision-makers

Please provide additional information here regarding the mandatory elements:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Please write your answer here:

9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please briefly describe the following aspects:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

9.8 Are indicators defined for national/regional GEP monitoring by the responsible authority?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify these indicators:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '146 [J98]' (9.8 Are indicators defined for national/regional GEP monitoring by the responsible authority?)

Please write your answer here:

9.9 Is the monitoring of GEPs part of the national/ regional monitoring system/ policy only, or is it related to ERA monitoring activities? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- ERA policy
- National/ regional policy
- Both
- Other

9.10 Does a publicly available database of GEPs exist at the national/regional level?

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide the link:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '149 [J910]' (9.10 Does a publicly available database of GEPs exist at the national/regional level?)

Please write your answer here:

9.11 Does this system measure impact in terms of the defined gender equality priorities (at national or international level)?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

9.12 Which features of GEPs does the system monitor? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- GEP is a publicly available document
- Dedicated resources are allocated for gender equality work
- System for collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data is in place
- Training and capacity building are planned
- Reporting on gender balance in leadership and decision-making
- Monitoring of gender equality in recruitment and promotion processes at the institutional level
- Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
- Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment are in place
- None of the above
- Other:

9.13 What impact on gender equality in your country have the following features of GEPs had (where 1= no impact, 5 = strong impact)?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	1	2	3	4	5
GEP is a publicly available document					
Dedicated resources are allocated for gender equality work					
System for collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data is in place					
Training and capacity					

**building are
planned**

**Reporting on
gender balance
in leadership
and decision-
making**

**Monitoring of
gender equality
in recruitment
and promotion
processes at
the
institutional
level**

**Integration of
the gender
dimension into
research and
teaching
content**

**Measures
against
gender-based
violence
including
sexual
harassment are
in place**

**Other, please
specify**

9.14 Does a national evaluation system exist for GEP implementation? *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- It is planned
- No, and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please describe its main principles and the periodicity of the GEP implementation evaluation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '154 [J914]' (9.14 Does a national evaluation system exist for GEP implementation?)

Please write your answer here:

10. Relevant stakeholders and organisations

Note: the stakeholder organisations need not focus only on gender equality but could be concerned with other relevant issues (race/ethnicity, LGBTQI+ rights, international mobility, PhD associations, early-career researcher associations, precarity, position of returning researchers after international mobility etc.)

10.1 Which national stakeholders active in the field of research, higher education and/or innovation (NGOs, citizens/students/researchers/other associations) would be suitable for cooperation with GENDERACTIONplus in relation to citizen and stakeholder engagement? Please, provide the requested information below.

10.2 Please add any other comments, ideas, or tips on public/citizen engagement:

Please write your answer here:

11. Final remarks

If there are aspects that this survey has not covered and you would like to share them, please add any comments here:

Please write your answer here:

Submit your survey.

Your response has been recorded. Thank you very much for your time!

Appendix B – Benchmark survey questions for RFOs

GENDERACTIONplus: BENCHMARKING OF RFO POLICIES

Scope and objectives: This is a benchmarking exercise of **RFO policies on gender equality in research, higher education and innovation** in the five thematic areas of GENDERACTIONplus (intersectionality and inclusiveness; gender-based violence; gender dimension in research, innovation and teaching; monitoring and evaluation in the ERA; institutional change through gender equality plans). **The objective is to establish what is in place at the RFO level and what are emerging good practices we can learn from.**

Background: In 2021, gender equality in higher education, research and innovation has been reaffirmed as a priority for the new European Research Area (ERA).¹ By end of June 2022, Member States have indicated their interest in addressing ERA Action 5 (Gender equality and inclusiveness). New policy areas identified include intersectionality and inclusiveness and gender-based violence in academia. Further policy attention is required in the areas of the gender dimension in teaching, research and innovation; monitoring and evaluation of ERA policies and advancing institutional change through Gender Equality Plans, including monitoring and evaluation of the impact of GEPs on gender equality.

This benchmark is then to set ground for current policies and developments at the RFO level as relevant; as such, it will be an important contribution to ERA Policy Action 5.

Timeframe: 2017 – present time unless specified otherwise; the focus is on policies that are in force now and recent evolution

Who should complete: One answer per RFO is requested. Project partners (both beneficiaries and Associated Partners) are responsible for coordinating input to the benchmark with other relevant national bodies (if necessary).

The deadline for providing your input in the LimeSurvey is 6 November 2022.

Main definitions

- **Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)** are defined as any public or private body financing research.
- **Law** is a set of rules that are created and enforceable by social or governmental institutions to regulate behaviour, adopted through a defined legislative process.
- **Policy** is a deliberate system of guidelines to guide decisions and achieve policy outcomes. It is a statement of intent and is implemented as a procedure or a protocol. Policies are generally adopted by a governance body within an organization. For the purpose of this benchmark, policies are defined as adopted by national or regional governments in the form of official regulations, procedures officially adopted by the governing body in the form of a document.
- **Policy measure** is intended to mean an action taken by the national / regional authority that may be one-off, not embedded in a policy document.

A [glossary](#) is attached providing definitions of key concepts.

Notes:

- **in the case of requests for document translations to English, if there is/are no official document(s), machine translation(s) is/are sufficient;**

- **otherwise, an official institutional position is sought unless requested explicitly otherwise.**

There are 122 questions in this survey.

1. Background information

1.1 Partner institution *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- BULGARIAN NATIONAL SCIENCE FUND
- Czech Science Foundation
- Dutch Research Council
- Estonian Research Council
- Fonds de la Recherche Scientifique
- Forte, Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare
- FUNDACAO PARA A CIENCIA E A TECNOLOGIA
- German Research Foundation (DFG)
- Health Research Board
- Independent Research Fund Denmark, DFF
- Irish Research Council (through beneficiary HEA)
- Kilden at the Research Council of Norway
- Malta Council for Science and Technology, MCST
- Regional Foundation for Biomedical Research
- Research and Innovation Foundation
- Research Council Lithuania
- Science Foundation Ireland
- Technologická agentura České Republiky
- The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey
- Unitatea Executiva pentru Finantarea Invatamantului Superior, a Cercetarii, Dezvoltarii si Inovarii
- Vilnius University Šiauliai Academy
- VINNOVA SWEDISH AGENCY FOR INNOVATION SYSTEMS

1.3 Contact person for the benchmarking exercise *

Please write your answer here:

1.4 Email *

Please write your answer here:

2. Areas of research and innovation supported by the RFO

2.1 Your RFO is supporting: *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- All
- Basic research / blue skies
- Applied research

- Innovation
- Other:

2.2 What areas of research and/or innovation does your organization provide funding for?

*

Please choose **all** that apply:

- All
- Social sciences
- Humanities
- Natural sciences
- Agricultural sciences
- Medical and health sciences
- Engineering and technical sciences
- Interdisciplinary research
- Other:

2.3 What types of organisations are eligible for funding at your RFO? *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Public research institutions
- Private research institutions
- Public higher education institutions
- Private higher education institutions
- Small and medium-sized enterprises and start-ups
- Large companies
- Civil society organisations / non-governmental organisations
- Other:

3. Gender equality policies at the RFO level

3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

3.1.1 Are any actions or measures in place to advance gender equality at your RFO? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

3.2 When was it adopted? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please write your answer here:

3.3 Is there a responsible unit/person for implementing the policy? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify the position/unit responsible.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '10 [C312]' (3.3 Is there a responsible unit/person for implementing the policy?)

Please write your answer here:

3.4 Is this policy an internal Gender Equality Plan that complies with the Horizon Europe GEP requirement (covering the four building blocks)? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

3.5 What resources are allocated to implement your RFO's gender equality policy (allocated budget, time, personnel)? Please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please write your answer here:

3.6a Please provide a name(s) and link(s) to the policy/ies mentioned in this overview section, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation of the relevant text of the policy (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '8 [C31a]' (3.1.1 Are any actions or measures in place to advance gender equality at your RFO?)

Please write your answer here:

3.6b If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '8 [C31a]' (3.1.1 Are any actions or measures in place to advance gender equality at your RFO?)

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

3.7 What are the most important policy developments on gender equality at your RFO in the last two years? *

Please write your answer here:

3.8 What have been the main facilitating factors for these developments? *

Please write your answer here:

3.9 Does your RFO have a GEP eligibility criterion in place toward host institutions of applicants? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Other

3.9.1 Has this GEP eligibility criterion been introduced in response to the Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [C35]' (3.9 Does your RFO have a GEP eligibility criterion in place toward host institutions of applicants?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

3.9.2 Is the GEP criterion compulsory to access your calls for proposals or tenders? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [C35]' (3.9 Does your RFO have a GEP eligibility criterion in place toward host institutions of applicants?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

3.9.3 If not, does having a GEP provide a bonus in the evaluation process? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '18 [C35]' (3.9 Does your RFO have a GEP eligibility criterion in place toward host institutions of applicants?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

3.9.4 If your RFO does not have a GEP eligibility criterion for applicants, has the Horizon Europe GEP requirement had any other effect at your RFO? (Please provide any other relevant information about the effect of the GEP eligibility criterion or discussions surrounding it that will help to better understand and contextualise the information provided in the survey): *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '18 [C35]' (3.9 Does your RFO have a GEP eligibility criterion in place toward host institutions of applicants?)

Please write your answer here:

3.10 What have been the main hindering factors or barriers for advancing gender equality policy/ policy measures at your RFO, for the internal policies? (e.g., equality among employees, transparency in career progression, measures against discrimination, etc.) *

Please write your answer here:

3.11 Have any policies been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '24 [C37]' (3.11 Have any policies been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?)

Please write your answer here:

3.12 Have any measures / programmes of support been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify. *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '26 [C38]' (3.12 Have any measures / programmes of support been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?)

Please write your answer here:

3.13 Have any internal policies been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify. For example, this can be due to a reorientation of policy toward mainstreaming gender or framing issues as SDGs.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '28 [C39]' (3.13 Have any internal policies been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?)

Please write your answer here:

3.14 Have any measures / programmes addressing beneficiaries been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '30 [C310]' (3.14 Have any measures / programmes addressing beneficiaries been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?)

Please write your answer here:

3.15 What have been the main hindering factors for advancing gender equality policy/ policy measures at your RFO, for the beneficiaries of the grants? (regarding both gender equality in

research and innovation teams and the gender dimension in the content of the research and innovation project) *

Please write your answer here:

3.16 Have any policies been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '33 [C3120]' (3.16 Have any policies been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?)

Please write your answer here:

3.17 Have any measures / programmes of support been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '35 [C3130]' (3.17 Have any measures / programmes of support been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?)

Please write your answer here:

3.18 Have any internal policies been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify. For example, this can be due to the need to exclude potential beneficiaries that do not comply with GE requirements.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '37 [C3140]' (3.18 Have any internal policies been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?)

Please write your answer here:

3.19 Have any measures/programmes been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '39 [C315]' (3.19 Have any measures/programmes been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?)

Please write your answer here:

4. Intersectionality and inclusiveness

Intersectionality

The Commission has stated a wish to broaden gender equality policies in research and innovation to intersections with other potential grounds for discrimination such as ethnicity, disability and sexual orientation. This section of the survey serves to assess to what extent this is addressed in RFOs.

4.1 Does your RFO's gender equality policy also include one or more of the following dimensions? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- None
- Other:

4.2 Please specify the relevant passages of the document and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please write your answer here:

4.3 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your policy, what are the terms most frequently used? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- non-discrimination
- multiple discrimination (additive)
- intersectionality
- representation
- gender+ equality
- diversity
- inclusiveness/inclusion
- inclusive equality
- equity/equality
- Other:

4.4 Is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived policies or strategies at the level of your RFO (e.g., strategic plans, mission statement etc.)? Please provide examples: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '7 [C31]' (3.1 Does your RFO have a dedicated gender equality policy?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '44 [D45]' (4.4 Is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived policies or strategies at the level of your RFO (e.g., strategic plans, mission statement etc.)? Please provide examples:)

Please write your answer here:

4.5 Has your RFO faced any of the following obstacles in developing a policy including an intersectional approach? *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Lack of national policy in this field
- Uncertainty about the terminology to be used
- Lack of a unified understanding of the underlying concepts
- Gender equality as a policy topic is a struggle without other inequality grounds
- Resistance at management level at your institution
- Lack of human resources
- Lack of economic resources

- Lack of interest / not regarded to be relevant
- Lack of disaggregated data on ethnic and other minorities
- Lack of research-based knowledge on gender and diversity in research in your country
- None
- Other:

4.6 What initiatives and knowledge are needed to lift the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the agenda in your RFO?

Please write your answer here:

5. Inclusive research careers

The purpose of section 5 is mapping current and emerging strategies and policies on research careers. Through the information collected and analysed - pinpointing patterns, gaps and solutions, and deepening evidence-based knowledge - we will be able to develop strategic policy recommendations in order to promote more inclusive careers across MS, the main target of this part of the survey, approaching them from an intersectional perspective. This converges to the crucial challenge that is building the new ERA, a vision in line with the directions substantiated in the [Council Conclusions Deepening the European Research Area: Providing researchers with attractive and sustainable careers and working conditions and making brain circulation a reality](#), in the [Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe](#) and the [ERA Policy Agenda](#) (namely at the crossroad of actions 4 and 5).

Recognizing the growing role of RFOs in promoting gender-inclusive culture, this survey further aims at mapping particular framing conditions set by your institution with a diversified impact on the large spectrum of research careers.

5.1 Is your RFO involved in the discussions (as participating in expert groups, advisory bodies, other) on the research careers agenda? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, what is your role or contribution to the discussions on the research careers agenda? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '48 [E51]' (5.1 Is your RFO involved in the discussions (as participating in expert groups, advisory bodies, other) on the research careers agenda?)

Please write your answer here:

If not, why? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '48 [E51]' (5.1 Is your RFO involved in the discussions (as participating in expert groups, advisory bodies, other) on the research careers agenda?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- There is no discussion about inclusive research careers at all
- There is a discussion, but the national authority and the RFO are not articulated or not moving forward simultaneously

- Other:

5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.3 Has your RFO faced any of the following obstacles in developing strategies/ policies/ policy measures on gender inclusive careers? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Uncertainty about the terminology to be used
- Lack of a unified understanding of the underlying concepts
- Prevalent masculine notions about the research profession (total dedication, extreme focus on performance etc.)
- Not yet on the national agenda
- Still under preliminary debate
- Lack of political /societal awareness
- Lack of Gender Equality structures
- Budgetary constraints
- Lack of gender disaggregated data
- Other:

5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.5 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures identify any inequality grounds/diversity other than gender? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please check all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '54 [E523]' (5.5 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures identify any inequality grounds/diversity other than gender?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Religion
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Age
- Socio-economic background/class
- Political orientation
- Origin country
- Power relations
- Other:

5.6 Do these strategies/ policies/ policy measures have an intersectional perspective? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please indicate shortly the existing intersections. *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '56 [E524]' (5.6 Do these strategies/ policies/ policy measures have an intersectional perspective?)

Please write your answer here:

5.7a If available, provide a link to the document(s) online, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please write your answer here:

5.7b If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example?))

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.8 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality, what are the terms most frequently used in your policies and initiatives on inclusive research careers? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '54 [E523]' (5.5 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures identify any inequality grounds/diversity other than gender?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Non-discrimination
- Intersectionality
- Representation
- Gender+ equality
- Diversity
- Inclusiveness/inclusion
- Inclusive equality
- Equity/equality
- None of the above
- Other:

5.8.1 Please comment/explain especially if multiple terms are used: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '54 [E523]' (5.5 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures identify any inequality grounds/diversity other than gender?)

Please write your answer here:

5.8.2 Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation). *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example?))

Please write your answer here:

5.9 Within the above identified strategies/policies /policy measures, what gender sensitive actions/initiatives were designed? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Access to Employment: diversity and equality of opportunities in recruitment and selection processes
- Performance evaluation and career progression
- Gender balanced peer review panels/panel's chair
- Gender balance in funding schemes, by setting up gender related topics
- Gender balance in funding schemes, by setting up target groups
- Incentives to mobility, namely international, and to returns
- Return grants for parents after a career break
- Gender bias awareness through training / reflection / skills development for peer review panels and panel chairs
- Rewards 'Women in research', in particular in the under-represented areas
- Other:

Please tick all that apply.

5.9.1 What groups are targeted by the funding schemes? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '63 [E54]' (5.9 Within the above identified strategies/policies /policy measures, what gender sensitive actions/initiatives were designed?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- PhD
- Postdocs
- Early-career researchers
- Mid-career excellence,
- Senior excellence
- Other

Please, specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '64 [E541]' (5.9.1 What groups are targeted by the funding schemes?)

Please write your answer here:

5.9.2 Please specify the relevant passages in the above-mentioned document(s) and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation). *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at

question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please write your answer here:

5.10 Is attention to inclusive research careers policies or strategies a recent development (less than 3 years) or an established area of work in your institution (more than 3 years)? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Recent development
- Established area of work

Please specify: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please write your answer here:

5.11 Are these policies/policy instruments/programmes of support already implemented? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '53 [E521]' (5.4 Do these strategies/policies/policy measures promote gender equality (as programmes of support, for example)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.11.1 Is monitoring of these instruments in place, through any kind of evaluation process? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '69 [E56]' (5.11 Are these policies/policy instruments/programmes of support already implemented?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.11.2 What are the key factors for the success in implementation? Please share case studies or good practices that have helped your RFO in strengthening inclusive research careers.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [E52]' (5.2 Are there strategies/policies/policy measures addressing research careers in higher education and research institutions at your RFO?) and Answer was 'Yes' at question '69 [E56]' (5.11 Are these policies/policy instruments/programmes of support already implemented?)

Please write your answer here:

5.13 In the context of the social security system coverage, has your organisation implemented more favourable regulations or practices than the ones generally available/applied in the legal system (Labour Code)? Types of researcher positions - permanent or temporary – and PhD students with fellowships are to be considered. *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.13.1 If yes, please explain how, having in mind the following situations (illness, unemployment, work-life balance, maternity and parental leave / support - e.g., length and allowance during the leave, retirement, other - please describe).*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '72 [E57]' (5.13 In the context of the social security system coverage, has your organisation implemented more favourable regulations or practices than the ones generally available/applied in the legal system (Labour Code)? Types of researcher positions - permanent or temporary – and PhD students with fellowships are to be considered.)

Please write your answer here:

5.13.2 From your organisation's point of view, in which of the above situations does discrimination on gender mostly persist and how? (e.g., returning to work after a maternity /parental leave) *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '72 [E57]' (5.13 In the context of the social security system coverage, has your organisation implemented more favourable regulations or practices than the ones generally available/applied in the legal system (Labour Code)? Types of researcher positions - permanent or temporary – and PhD students with fellowships are to be considered.)

Please write your answer here:

5.14 Based on your experience, what recommendations could you provide to promote and improve the design and implementation of inclusive research careers?

Please write your answer here:

6. Gender-based violence

Instruction: Please read your country reports from the UniSAFE project available on the [Zenodo community](#) (please use the search box at the top of the page to search for your country's national report) and indicate any new developments at the level of your RFO since 2021 (please note that the UniSAFE project covers EU-27 and among the Associated Countries Iceland, UK, Serbia and Turkey).

Gender-Based Violence (GBV) is defined as all forms of gendered violations and abuse, including but not limited to, physical violence, psychological violence, economic and financial violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender harassment, stalking, organisational violence and harassment. GBV can occur in both online and offline contexts, and also includes emerging forms of violence, experienced as violence, violations and abuse not yet necessarily named or recognised as violence.

6.1 Does your RFO have a new or revised policy to address GBV in relation to the applicants, adopted since 1st of May 2021? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

6.2a If available, provide a link to the document(s) online, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '76 [F61]' (6.1 Does your RFO have a new or revised policy to address GBV in relation to the applicants, adopted since 1st of May 2021?)

Please write your answer here:

6.2b If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '76 [F61]' (6.1 Does your RFO have a new or revised policy to address GBV in relation to the applicants, adopted since 1st of May 2021?)

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.3 Does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '76 [F61]' (6.1 Does your RFO have a new or revised policy to address GBV in relation to the applicants, adopted since 1st of May 2021?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, tick off for which inequality grounds:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '79 [F612]' (6.3 Does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

Please add any possible details already known.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned ' at question '79 [F612]' (6.3 Does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned ' at question '79 [F612]' (6.3 Does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?)

Please write your answer here:

6.4 Has your RFO implemented any measures against GBV for the applicants in their funding schemes conditions since 1 May 2021? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '83 [E62]' (6.4 Has your RFO implemented any measures against GBV for the applicants in their funding schemes conditions since 1 May 2021?)

If it is planned, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '83 [E62]' (6.4 Has your RFO implemented any measures against GBV for the applicants in their funding schemes conditions since 1 May 2021?)

If no, please provide an explanation for why not:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '83 [E62]' (6.4 Has your RFO implemented any measures against GBV for the applicants in their funding schemes conditions since 1 May 2021?)

Please write your answer here:

6.5 Has your RFO introduced GBV as a priority topic in a funding scheme/programme to support research on GBV in universities and research organisations since 1 May 2021? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '87 [E63]' (6.5 Has your RFO introduced GBV as a priority topic in a funding scheme/programme to support research on GBV in universities and research organisations since 1 May 2021?)

If it is planned, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '87 [E63]' (6.5 Has your RFO introduced GBV as a priority topic in a funding scheme/programme to support research on GBV in universities and research organisations since 1 May 2021?)

If no, please provide an explanation for why not:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '87 [E63]' (6.5 Has your RFO introduced GBV as a priority topic in a funding scheme/programme to support research on GBV in universities and research organisations since 1 May 2021?)

Please write your answer here:

6.6 Has your RFO put in place any actions or measures regarding GBV for the safety of researchers participating in projects funded since 1 May 2021? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '91 [E64]' (6.6 Has your RFO put in place any actions or measures regarding GBV for the safety of researchers participating in projects funded since 1 May 2021?)

If it is planned, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '91 [E64]' (6.6 Has your RFO put in place any actions or measures regarding GBV for the safety of researchers participating in projects funded since 1 May 2021?)

If no, please provide an explanation for not why

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '91 [E64]' (6.6 Has your RFO put in place any actions or measures regarding GBV for the safety of researchers participating in projects funded since 1 May 2021?)

Please write your answer here:

6.7 Does your RFO have systems/procedures for getting info from RPOs on misconduct in terms of GBV perpetrated by Principal Investigators and/or researchers applying for funding? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '95 [E65]' (6.7 Does your RFO have systems/procedures for getting info from RPOs on misconduct in terms of GBV perpetrated by Principal Investigators and/or researchers applying for funding?)

Please write your answer here:

If it is planned, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '95 [E65]' (6.7 Does your RFO have systems/procedures for getting info from RPOs on misconduct in terms of GBV perpetrated by Principal Investigators and/or researchers applying for funding?)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '95 [E65]' (6.7 Does your RFO have systems/procedures for getting info from RPOs on misconduct in terms of GBV perpetrated by Principal Investigators and/or researchers applying for funding?)

Please write your answer here:

6.8 Are there any established procedures in your RFO for sanctioning perpetrators, when informed on misconduct in terms of GBV by an RPO? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '99 [F66]' (6.8 Are there any established procedures in your RFO for sanctioning perpetrators, when informed on misconduct in terms of GBV by an RPO?)

Please write your answer here:

If it is planned, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '99 [F66]' (6.8 Are there any established procedures in your RFO for sanctioning perpetrators, when informed on misconduct in terms of GBV by an RPO?)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '99 [F66]' (6.8 Are there any established procedures in your RFO for sanctioning perpetrators, when informed on misconduct in terms of GBV by an RPO?)

Please write your answer here:

6.9 Do you know of any current ideas or suggestions proposed among the other RFOs in your country, targeting preventing GBV in research in the future through specific actions or measures? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '103 [F67]' (6.9 Do you know of any current ideas or suggestions proposed among the other RFOs in your country, targeting preventing GBV in research in the future through specific actions or measures?)

7. Gender dimension in research and innovation

This section focuses specifically on RFOs initiatives to promote the integration of the gender dimension in the content of research and innovation projects (i.e., sex/gender analysis in R&I). **Note that these questions are not about gender balance in R&I teams.** We encourage you to check our glossary for clarification of the concepts related to this section link to the [glossary](#).

7.1 What kind of actions has your RFO taken to promote the integration of the gender dimension into R&I? Please tick all that apply: *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Financial incentives/support to promote the gender dimension in research and innovation
- A specific funding programme on gender studies is in place
- Requiring applicants to specify whether they are considering sex and/or gender in their research/ innovation proposal
- Inclusion of gender experts in the research and innovation teams is encouraged in the R&I calls
- Training on sex/gender analysis for the research and innovation team is considered as an eligible cost in the RFO funding schemes
- Established processes to evaluate the integration of the sex/gender analysis into R&I (i.e., as part of the institution's mandate and through well-established guidelines on the evaluation)
- Positive action measures to favour projects that integrate sex and/or gender (go to the glossary for a definition of positive action measures)
- Guidelines on the gender dimension of R&I for applicants
- Guidelines on the gender dimension of R&I for evaluators
- Training on the gender dimension of R&I for applicants
- Training on the gender dimension of R&I for evaluators
- Experts on gender in R&I are included in the evaluation committees
- Communication campaign to make visible the support to sex/gender analysis
- Dissemination materials on the gender dimension in R&I available (videos, academic papers, leaflets...)
- Other:

7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

7.3a If available, provide a link to the RFO official policy related to the information requested above and other supporting documents you consider relevant for the analysis. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

7.3b If not publicly available online, please upload the RFO official policy related to the information requested above and other supporting documents you consider relevant for the analysis. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

7.4 What kind of strategy or policy has your RFO adopted? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- National law
- Specific strategy / policy / measure (e.g. gender equality plan)
- Other:

7.5 What are the main goals of your strategy or policy? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

7.6 Does your strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I include an intersectional approach? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, tick off for which inequality grounds: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '111 [G75]' (7.6 Does your strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I include an intersectional approach?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity

- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

7.7 Does your strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I include the innovation and private sectors in the objective of producing non-biased knowledge and solutions for society? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

7.8 How is the strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I implemented? Please provide information on the unit(s) responsible for implementing the policy, the actions taken so far, and the structures developed for its implementation, including technical, human and economic resources. *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

7.9 How is the strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I monitored? Please provide information on the actions and structures, if any, established to supervise the concrete actions developed by the RFO/other agents of the R&I system, the indicators used and their outcomes. *

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

7.10 Has the strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I been evaluated? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

What impact or outcome has your policy on the gender dimension in R&I made? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '116 [G79]' (7.10 Has the strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I been evaluated?)

Please write your answer here:

7.11 Please explain the challenges/obstacles, if any, that your RFO has faced in implementing this policy or strategy on the gender dimension in R&I: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

7.12 If no, does your RFO plan to make a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '106 [G72]' (7.2 Does your RFO have a specific strategy or policy aimed at integrating the gender dimension into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please explain the context of the plans: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '119 [G721]' (7.12 If no, does your RFO plan to make a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

7.13 What would your RFO need to advance some of the measures mentioned above or others to promote sex and gender analyses and integration of the gender dimension in the R&I content? *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Financial resources
- More awareness on the relevance on sex/gender analysis for R&I
- Exchange experiences on how to consider the gender dimension in R&I from an intersectional perspective
- Capacity-building
- Training materials

- Mandatory policies (e.g., conditional funding)
- Other:

Please tick all that apply.

8. Relevant stakeholders and organisations

The stakeholder organisations need not focus only on gender equality but could be concerned with other relevant issues (incubators, innovation offices, knowledge transfer centres as well as race/ethnicity, LGBTQI+ rights, international mobility, PhD associations, early-career researcher associations, precarity, position of returning researchers after international mobility etc.).

8.1 Are there stakeholders for your RFO in the areas of gender equality, diversity, inclusiveness that may be relevant for citizen/stakeholder engagement in the GENDERACTIONplus project?

Submit your survey.

Your response has been recorded. Thank you very much for your time!

